

Hereditary diffuse gastric cancer spectrum associated with germline *CTNNA1* loss of function revealed by clinical and molecular data from 351 carrier families and over 37.000 non-carrier controls

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Abstract

Background: Diffuse gastric cancer (DGC) is the most common manifestation in germline *CTNNA1* variant carriers, with one study estimating a 49–57% lifetime risk by age 80. Knowledge on *CTNNA1*-associated Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer (HDGC), loss-of-function mechanisms, variant-type causality, disease spectrum and cancer-risks remain scarce.

Objective: Explore *CTNNA1* genotype-phenotype associations to improve genetic testing criteria, surveillance and risk-reduction recommendations for carriers.

Design: Using molecular, clinical and population data from 1308 individuals from 351 *CTNNA1*-variant carrier families and 37,428 non-carriers from European and American ancestries, we analysed genotype–phenotype associations with multivariable logistic regression. With CRISPR/Cas9 *CTNNA1*-knockout gastric cancer (GC) cells and *CTNNA1*-humanized *Drosophila*, we assessed *CTNNA1*-associated loss-of-function mechanisms.

Results: *CTNNA1*-truncating transcripts are degraded by Nonsense mediated mRNA decay (NMD), and DGCs from germline *CTNNA1*-truncating carriers lose α E-catenin. These transcripts are non-functional in *Drosophila*, in contrast to non-truncating transcripts. DGC risk is 8-fold higher in truncating, compared to non-truncating carriers. The risk of GC and LBC development in *CTNNA1*-truncating variant carriers is 5-fold and 8-fold lower than in *CDH1* pathogenic/likely pathogenic variant carriers, respectively. Compared to wild-type individuals, GC risk is 7-fold higher in *CTNNA1*-truncating and 38-fold in *CDH1*-truncating variant carriers. Lobular breast cancer is recurrent among *CTNNA1*-truncating carriers, some lacking HDGC-criteria. Simplification of previous criteria for *CTNNA1* genetic testing produced the ‘Porto’ criteria, which increased *CTNNA1*-carrier families’ pick-up rate by 9%, without performance loss compared to the HDGC 2020 clinical guidelines. Macular dystrophy patterned-2 was positively associated with non-truncating variants, specifically in α E-catenin M-fragment.

Conclusion: We provide compelling evidence supporting that *CTNNA1*-truncating variants positively associate with DGC and LBC, and NMD as the pathophysiological mechanism leading to *CTNNA1* downregulation. We demonstrate that compared to *CDH1*, *CTNNA1* is a moderate penetrance HDGC gene. This new knowledge is essential to define surveillance and/or prophylactic measures for *CTNNA1*-carrier individuals and families.

Introduction

CTNNA1 (HGNC:2509; ENSG00000044115; MIM#116805; NM_001903) is a tumour suppressor gene encoding the adherens' junction protein α E-catenin (P35221) [1-3]. α E-catenin binds to β -catenin, forming the E-cadherin/ β -catenin/ α E-catenin complex, which links E-cadherin to the actin cytoskeleton [2-7]. E-cadherin loss of function (LoF) is the best-known cause of hereditary diffuse gastric cancer (HDGC), a syndrome predisposing to early-onset diffuse gastric cancer (DGC) and lobular breast cancer (LBC) [8, 9]. Since 2013, 13 HDGC families and 12 macular dystrophy patterned 2 (MDPT2) families were found to carry *CTNNA1* germline variants [10-20]. Whereas germline *CTNNA1*-truncating variants were found in HDGC families, MDPT2 families harboured mainly missense variants [21]. Germline *CTNNA1*-truncating variants occur in approximately 2% of all HDGC-suspected families, while *CDH1*-truncating variants occur in 10%-40%, depending on geographical origin [13, 22-25].

In 2020, the International Gastric Cancer Linkage Consortium (IGCLC) updated the HDGC clinical practice guidelines and introduced *CTNNA1* as a *bona-fide* HDGC gene, recommending *CTNNA1* genetic testing in *CDH1*-negative HDGC-suspected families [22]. Guidelines recommend that carriers of *CTNNA1* pathogenic variants undergo yearly endoscopic surveillance, with consideration for prophylactic gastrectomy depending on biopsy results and DGC family history. Breast surveillance should be considered on a case-by-case basis, given the uncertainty regarding *CTNNA1*-related predisposition to LBC [22].

A literature review of 41 families, carrying 31 rare germline *CTNNA1* variants, revealed that truncating variants may also occur in families lacking HDGC-associated phenotypes, and are very rare in LBC-enriched families [14]. These observations and the small number of published *CTNNA1*-associated families challenge the current knowledge on *CTNNA1*-associated diseases, and are insufficient to understand disease spectrum, disease-associated molecular mechanisms, and to clarify variant-type causalities. This knowledge gap hampers the design of clinical management recommendations, particularly those with preventive intent, targeted to germline *CTNNA1*-variant carriers and families. Analysis of large clinical datasets integrated with detailed and curated molecular/functional data are, therefore, needed to optimize the pathway-of-care for germline *CTNNA1* variant carriers.

CDH1 transcripts bearing premature termination codons (PTC) are targeted for degradation by the nonsense mediated mRNA decay (NMD) machinery, being this the accepted disease mechanism for *CDH1*-associated HDGC [26, 27]. NMD degrades transcripts containing a PTC before the last exon-exon junction of a gene (NMD-competent region), preventing aberrant transcripts' expression [28]. In *CDH1*, PTC bearing transcripts after the NMD-competent region escape NMD, rarely occur in HDGC families, and are predicted to produce smaller E-cadherins retaining residual function [26, 29]. Although most *CTNNA1*-associated HDGC families described in the literature carry a PTC before the last exon-exon junction [11, 14], NMD remains to be proven as the associated LoF mechanism.

The current lack of knowledge on *CTNNA1*-related predisposition and pathogenesis is also preventing the design of variant classification guidelines to define clinical actionability.

Here, we present an in-depth analysis of the largest dataset of *CTNNA1*-variant carrier families to date, *CTNNA1*-associated disease phenotypes, and rare germline *CTNNA1* variants. This dataset, combined with *in vitro* and *in vivo* models, helps to clarify the mechanisms linked to *CTNNA1* LoF. We demonstrate that DGC is more likely to occur in *CTNNA1*-truncating than non-truncating variant carriers, while MDPT2 is more likely to occur in carriers of *CTNNA1*-non-truncating variants, specifically occurring in the α E-catenin M-fragment domain. LBC is rare but recurrent, and occurs concomitantly with DGC in families carrying truncating variants. We establish degradation of *CTNNA1* PTC bearing transcripts by NMD as the most likely mechanism of disease, while LoF caused by non-truncating *CTNNA1* variants is unlikely, based on our *Drosophila CTNNA1*-humanized model. We propose clinical criteria for *CTNNA1* genetic testing and demonstrate that these improve the pick-up rate of *CTNNA1*-associated HDGC and outperforms other sets of clinical criteria, currently used in the clinics. Our data also shows that truncating variant carriers present increased likelihood of developing GC compared to *CTNNA1* wild-type (WT) individuals. This is the first, and largest study, providing the clinical and molecular landscape of *CTNNA1*-associated diseases, while delivering *CTNNA1*-associated disease mechanisms and study models, with particular utility for *CTNNA1* carrier management and variant classification.

Methods

All methods used throughout this study are detailed in the Supplementary methods.

i. Patient cohorts: protocols and data collection

From October 1st, 2020 until March 31st, 2024, we retrospectively collected molecular and clinical data from 351 families (1308 individuals) carrying rare germline *CTNNA1* variants from different geographical origins. We curated *CTNNA1*-associated disease phenotypes and performed genotype-phenotype associations between carriers of different *CTNNA1* germline variants (Cohorts-I, -II and -III). We also collected retrospective clinical data on 270 *CTNNA1*-truncating variant carriers, 414 *CDH1* pathogenic/likely pathogenic (P/LP) variant carriers and 37,428 *CDH1* and *CTNNA1* WT individuals from the USA genetic testing company Ambry Genetics (Cohort-IV), to further analyse the likelihood of cancer development in *CTNNA1*-truncating or *CDH1* pathogenic variant carrier patients, compared to WT individuals. Study cohort layout is shown in Fig.1a, detailed in Supplementary Fig.1, Supplementary methods and in Supplementary Tables 1-3.

ii. Data collection of CTNNA1 variant carrier families: study protocol

We recruited and collected clinical and molecular information from families or individuals carrying a rare *CTNNA1* germline variant, irrespective of the phenotype or clinical history, and lacking germline P/LP variants in other tumour risk syndromes associated genes, including *CDH1*. Similar clinical and molecular information on additional families was collected from papers published in the literature until 2024. The questionnaire presented to collaborating institutions requested detailed family history, *CTNNA1* carrier status and kinship. Only disease phenotypes reported in 1st or 2nd degree and/or confirmed carrier relatives were included in the analysis (Fig.1a). The reason underlying the genetic testing request was not part of the questionnaire.

iii. Clinical criteria driving testing of CTNNA1 germline variants: definition, allocation and performance

We allocated each family into different sets of HDGC criteria. Here, the 'HDGC-Classic' criteria represent a combination of all criteria by Blair et al. 2020 [22] and Garcia-Pelaez et al 2023 [8], and were used as the baseline for analysis. Patients or families meeting HDGC Classic criteria were defined as HDGC-Classic families. Those with personal and/or familial history of DGC and/or LBC and/or GC that do not fulfil HDGC Classic criteria were defined as 'HDGC-Classic borderline' families. We considered DGC, LBC, and GC of unknown pathology as HDGC-related phenotypes. We tested the performance of the 'Classic' criteria, as well as other sets of criteria previously published

(‘Yale’ criteria) [30] or herein proposed (‘CTNNA1 expanded’ and ‘Porto’ criteria) using an equivalence and noninferiority test. For details see Supplementary methods.

Figure 1. Study design, cohorts' description and list of HDGC-Classic criteria. (a) 351 families carrying rare *CTNNA1* germline variants were categorized in three cohorts for sequential analysis. Patients or families meeting HDGC-Classic criteria (criteria by Blair et al. 2020 or by García-Pelaez et al. 2023) were herein defined as HDGC-Classic families. Those with personal and/or familial history of DGC and/or LBC and/or GC, lacking HDGC-Classic criteria, were herein defined as HDGC-Classic borderline families. Cohort-I comprises European carrier families, independently of the disease phenotypes; Cohort-II comprises non-European families with a

personal and/or family's history suggestive of HDGC (history of DGC, GC and/or LBC, regardless of age); Cohort-III comprises all carrier families not meeting HDGC-Classic criteria; (b) Frequency analysis of phenotypes in families from Cohort-I to define a cut-off level for phenotype analysis (all phenotypes with a frequency lower than LBC were included in OTHER category); (c) descriptive analysis of the most frequent phenotypes in Cohort-I: comparison between phenotypes in probands and direct blood relatives and the respective age at diagnosis; (d) Allocation of carrier families from Cohort-I to HDGC-Classic criteria [8, 22]. Bp – base-pair; HDGC – hereditary diffuse gastric cancer; DGC – diffuse gastric cancer; UNS-BC – breast cancer unspecified histotype; MDPT2 – macular dystrophy patterned 2; GC – gastric cancer unspecified histotype; CRC – colorectal cancer; PC – prostate cancer; OC – ovarian cancer; LBC – lobular breast cancer; PCC – pancreatic cancer; MEL – melanoma; UNK – unknown; LC – lung cancer; BRC – brain cancer; LEU – leukaemia; MG – multinodular goitre; SKC – skin cancer (non-melanoma); KC – kidney cancer; BDC – bladder cancer; UrC – urothelial cancer; POLYP – polyposis; LYMP – lymphoma; UtC – uterine cancer; CXC – cervical cancer; LVC – liver cancer; OEC – oesophageal cancer; H&N – head and neck cancer; TsC – testicular cancer; GyC – gynaecological cancer; AxC – appendix cancer; GBC – gallbladder cancer; SARC – sarcoma; EC – endometrial cancer; NT – neuroendocrine tumour; CLP – cleft lip/palate; EPE – epileptic encephalopathy; HYP – hypodontia; MIC – microdontia; PEC – peritoneal carcinosis; SD – standard deviation; P – proband; R – 1st or 2nd blood relative (3rd or higher when carrier status is confirmed).

iv. Data collection from CTNNA1 variant carrier families: cohorts' description

In all Cohorts, only phenotypes reported in 1st or 2nd degree and/or confirmed carrier relatives were included. Cohort-I (Europe): 71 families carrying 54 different *CTNNA1* variants with 71 carrier probands and 150 relatives (70 with confirmed carrier status). Cohort-I presented 39 different disease phenotypes occurring 223 times in 221 individuals. Cohort-II (North America): 59 families carrying 37 different *CTNNA1* germline variants with 59 carrier probands and 250 relatives (14 with confirmed carrier status). Cohort-II presented 38 different disease phenotypes occurring 340 times in 309 individuals. Cohort-II families were selected based on HDGC suspicion (personal and/or family history of DGC, and/or GC, and/or LBC). Cohort-III: 221 *CTNNA1* germline variant carrier families not meeting HDGC criteria. 221 carrier probands and 556 relatives (21 with confirmed carrier status), with a total of 798 disease phenotypes (Fig.1a). Supplementary Fig.1 provides a schematic representation of the recruitment of individuals and families included in Cohorts-I, -II and -III. Sixty-five *CTNNA1* germline variant carrier families were recruited from the clinics and 278 were contributed by clinical genetics laboratories from Europe and the US. The remaining families were published in the literature. Cohort-IV: 270 individuals with a germline truncating *CTNNA1* variant; 414 individuals with a *CDH1* P/LP germline variant (Supplementary Table 4); 37,428 individuals *CTNNA1* and *CDH1* WT that serve as control group. Cohort-IV individuals were identified via colon, gastric, breast cancer and pan-cancer susceptibility multigene panel testing and had no P/LP variants detected in genes from the panel used. Cohorts' clinical data is detailed in Fig.1a, Supplementary Fig.1 and Supplementary Tables 1-3.

v. Data collection from CTNNA1 variant carrier families: analysis' description

Analysis-A, -B, -C and -D were designed to answer specific clinical questions. Analysis-A aimed to analyse the *CTNNA1*-associated disease spectrum and genotype-phenotype associations in the European setting. For that, Cohort-I families were divided according to *CTNNA1* variant molecular consequence (truncating vs. non-truncating). Analysis-B focused on finding the best set of criteria driving genetic testing in *CTNNA1* suspected families. For that, all HDGC-classic and HDGC-Classic borderline families from Cohort-I and Cohort-II with a truncating variant were analysed. Analysis-C compared the likelihood of GC or LBC development in carriers of truncating *CTNNA1* and P/LP *CDH1* germline variants in Cohort-IV. Analysis-D aimed to uncover genotype-phenotype associations beyond the HDGC context. For that, only carrier families not meeting the 'Porto' criteria were analysed (Cohort-I: 46 families; Cohort-II: 28 families; Cohort-III: 221 families). Families were divided according to *CTNNA1* variant molecular consequence (truncating vs. non-truncating). Fig.1a details Analysis-A, -B, -C and -D.

vi. Patient and public involvement

Patients or the public were not involved in the design, or conduct, or reporting, or dissemination plans of our research.

Results

i. HDGC-associated phenotypes are common in European families carrying CTNNA1 variants

Cohort-I enclosed 71 European families carrying rare germline *CTNNA1* variants (Fig.1b; Supplementary Table 5). DGC and unspecified breast cancer (UNS-BC) were the most frequent phenotypes, each with 19.7% (44/223) and an average age-of-onset (\bar{x} AO; mean \pm standard deviation) of 47.3 ± 13.7 years old (yo) and 50.6 ± 12.1 yo, respectively (Fig.1c). DGC, GC and LBC, herein considered HDGC-related phenotypes, accounted for ~30% of all disease phenotypes (Fig.1c). Among DGC cases, small intramucosal signet ring cell carcinomas (pT1a lesions) were reported in nine direct blood relatives with confirmed carrier status from probands with advanced DGC in three families (Supplementary Table 6).

In Cohort-I, 33.8% (24/71) of the families met HDGC-Classic criteria [8, 22] (Fig.1d). DGC-centred 'Classic' criteria C1 (45.8%; 11/24) and C4 (33.3%; 8/24), as well as LBC-related C10 and C11 (12.5%; 3/24) (Fig.1d), were the most frequent. Interestingly, 83% (20/24) of HDGC families meeting 'Classic' criteria carried *CTNNA1*-truncating variants

(Fig.1a), raising the hypothesis that complete loss of *CTNNA1* expression may be the *CTNNA1*-associated HDGC disease mechanism.

ii. CTNNA1 transcripts bearing PTCs before the last exon-exon junction are degraded by NMD and DGC tumours from CTNNA1-truncating carriers lack α E-catenin expression

We CRISPR/Cas9 engineered the MKN74 gastric cancer (GC) cell line to obtain a truncating *CTNNA1* homozygous variant, by deleting the out-of-frame exon 11 (*CTNNA1_EX11Del*). *CTNNA1_EX11Del* cells presented 33-fold and 5.3-fold decrease in *CTNNA1* mRNA and protein expression, respectively, compared to WT ($p < 0.0001$ and $p = 0.0115$), resulting in complete loss of α E-catenin expression (Supplementary Fig.2). Treatment of *CTNNA1_EX11Del* cells with a NMD blocker (cycloheximide) rescued *CTNNA1* mRNA expression by 13-fold ($p < 0.05$), while no significant increase was observed in WT cells (Fig.2a). Rescued *CTNNA1* mRNA expression in *CTNNA1_EX11Del* was similar to WT cells (Fig.2b). Furthermore, α E-catenin immunostaining analysis revealed that DGCs from *CTNNA1*-truncating carriers displayed complete loss of α E-catenin expression in tumours, but not in the normal adjacent mucosa (Fig.2c). These results establish degradation of *CTNNA1* truncated transcripts by NMD as a likely *CTNNA1*-associated disease mechanism.

iii. CTNNA1 Drosophila-humanized model consolidates truncating variants as LoF, while demonstrating α E-catenin WT function for non-truncating variants

We tested the functional impact of *CTNNA1* variants in a *Drosophila melanogaster* *CTNNA1*-humanized model. We knockdown *Drosophila* α -catenin ($D\alpha$ -cat KD) and replaced it by its human homolog cDNA (*hCTNNA1*), either WT or mutated (Supplementary methods; Supplementary Tables 2 and 7). Immunofluorescence on 3rd instar larvae revealed successful rescue of *CTNNA1* expression (Fig.2d; in green) in $D\alpha$ -cat KD (Fig.2d; in red) by *hCTNNA1* WT and p.Glu70Lys missense variant (Fig.2d), but not by p.Gln675* truncating variant (Fig.2d). Analysis on adults' survival (AS) showed that $D\alpha$ -cat loss during development led to 5.3-fold adult survival decrease relative to control ($p < 0.0001$) (Fig.2e). WT *hCTNNA1* and p.Glu70Lys missense rescued AS to control levels ($p < 0.0001$). In contrast, p.Gln675* nonsense variant could not rescue AS, displaying a 4.1-fold AS decrease compared to WT *hCTNNA1* ($p = 0.0005$) (Fig.2e). WT *hCTNNA1* and p.Glu70Lys missense variant expression allowed eye development in $D\alpha$ -cat KD flies, both displaying near-normal retinal cell proliferation and differentiation, while p.Gln675* nonsense variant expression did not (Fig.2f). These data consolidate truncating variants, but not missense variants, as LoF.

Figure 2. Development of in vitro and in vivo models to understand the functional impact of CTNNA1 variants. An in vitro model was created to assess the effect of NMD over *CTNNA1* transcripts bearing a premature termination codon. The *CTNNA1* wild-type (WT) MKN74 cell line was genetically edited by CRISPR/Cas9 to delete the out-of-frame exon 11 (MKN74 Ex11Del), to mimic a truncating variant in the *CTNNA1* NMD-competent region (Supplementary Fig.2). (a) NMD blockade using cycloheximide leads to increased mRNA expression in Ex11Del cells but not in WT cell line; (b) NMD blockade rescued *CTNNA1* mRNA transcripts' expression, in Ex11Del cells, to similar levels of MKN74 WT. An in vivo humanized *Drosophila melanogaster* model was generated targeting the eye was generated. (c) H&E staining and immunostaining for human α -catenin in DGC FFPE samples from three patients carrying *CTNNA1*-truncating variants. Scale bars represent a distance of 50 μ m. *Drosophila* α -catenin protein (D α -cat) was replaced by the human α -catenin protein counterpart (H α -cat) in the undifferentiated eye progenitors from the eye-antennal imaginal disk. (d) D α -cat (in red) and H α -cat (in green) expression in eye-antennal imaginal disk from 3rd instar larvae. White scale bars represent a distance of 50 μ m; dashed white line represents the targeted area. (e) Survival analysis of adult flies carrying WT or mutant *CTNNA1* transcripts; (f) Eye phenotype analysis in adult flies carrying WT or mutant *CTNNA1* transcripts. Statistically significant results were established by two-tailed paired t-test (* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$; **** $p < 0.0001$). KD – knockdown; WT – wild-type; H&E – Haematoxylin and Eosin; D α – *Drosophila* α -catenin, H α – Human α -catenin, yo – years old, LoF – loss-of-function, DGC – diffuse gastric cancer, TNM – tumour nodes, metastasis, n.s. – not significant.

iv. Carriers of germline CTNNA1-truncating variants are more likely to develop DGC than non-truncating variants carriers

We formally analysed genotype-phenotype associations in Cohort-I (Analysis-A). For that, we divided Cohort-I into truncating (n=27 families; 38%) and non-truncating (n=44 families; 62%) variant carrier families. From 27 truncating families, 74% (20/27) met HDGC-Classic criteria [8, 22] (Fig.3a). In these families, HDGC-related phenotypes represented 51.8% (58/112) and presented early \bar{x} AO (DGC:48.0 \pm 14.2yo; GC:50.3 \pm 8.6yo; LBC:53.4 \pm 17.4yo) in both probands and direct blood relatives (Fig.3a). In contrast, HDGC-associated phenotypes only represented 6% (7/111) of all disease phenotypes from non-truncating families (Fig.3a). Here, the most frequent phenotype was UNS-BC, which displayed a lower \bar{x} AO (48.3 \pm 11.7yo) compared to truncating carriers (55.6 \pm 11.6yo) (Fig.3a). MDPT2 was restricted to non-truncating non-HDGC families (Fig.3a). Firth's bias-reduced multivariate logistic regression formally assessed the likelihood of occurrence of each disease phenotype in truncating or non-truncating carrier families (Fig.3b). Truncating carriers displayed a significant 8-fold and 4.8-fold increased likelihood of developing DGC and GC, respectively, relative to non-truncating carriers (DGC: OR=8.33; 95%CI [3.125-25]; $p < 0.00001$; GC: OR=4.76; 95%CI [1.316-25]; $p = 0.0151$) (Fig.3b). A positive tendency was observed for an association between LBC with truncating variants (OR=4.76; 95%CI [0.98-50]; $p = 0.053$) (Fig.3b; Supplementary Table 8). Cancer phenotypes not classically related to HDGC, namely colorectal (CRC), ovarian (OC) and prostate (PC) cancers, were not enriched in any group and were generally diagnosed at a later onset (Fig.3a and 3b; Supplementary Table 8).

Figure 3. Genotype-phenotype correlations in CTNNA1 variant carrier families. (a) Genotype-phenotype analysis in Cohort-I; families were grouped as carriers of CTNNA1 variants predicted to cause truncation (truncating) or not (non-truncating) of α E-catenin; In graphic bars, full colour represent the fraction of phenotypes in families meeting 'Classic' HDGC criteria, while lack of colour represents the fraction of phenotypes in families not meeting those criteria (b) Multivariable Firth's bias-reduced penalized-likelihood logistic regression analysis was used to determine the likelihood of each disease phenotype development in Cohort-I (Truncating vs Non-truncating) ($p < 0.05$); (c) Phenotypes distribution in probands and relatives in Cohort-II; In graphic bars, full colour represent the fraction of phenotypes in families meeting 'Classic' HDGC criteria, while lack of colour represents the fraction of phenotypes in families not meeting those criteria; (d) Distribution of the 'Classic' and 'CTNNA1 extended' HDGC clinical criteria for genetic testing in families carrying truncating CTNNA1 germline variants and with a clinical suspicion of HDGC (personal and/or family history of DGC, GC and/or LBC) (includes families from Cohort-I and Cohort-II); (e) Distribution of HDGC-associated phenotypes in families from Cohort-I (Europe) and Cohort-II (North America) meeting the 'Classic + CTNNA1 extended' criteria. Bars with stripes represent Cohort-I and bars with points represent Cohort-II. HDGC – hereditary diffuse gastric cancer; DGC – diffuse gastric cancer; LBC – lobular breast cancer; GC – gastric cancer unspecified histotype; UNS-BC – breast cancer unspecified histotype; CRC – colorectal cancer; OC – ovarian cancer; PC – prostate cancer; MDPT2 – macular dystrophy patterned 2; SD – standard deviation; P – proband; R – 1st or 2nd blood relative (3rd or higher when carrier status is confirmed).

v. North American families carrying CTNNA1-truncating variants validate the association with HDGC phenotypes found in the European cohort

To validate the HDGC-associated disease spectrum, we conducted Analysis-B in 59 North American families displaying personal and/or family history of DGC, and/or GC,

and/or LBC at any age, and carrying rare germline *CTNNA1* variants (Cohort-II; Supplementary Tables 2 and 3). 92% (54/59) carried truncating variants, reinforcing the positive association of *CTNNA1*-truncating variants with HDGC-related phenotypes. Although these families consistently presented a clinical history of HDGC-related phenotypes, only 46% (25/54) met the 'Classic' criteria, compared to 74% (20/27) in Cohort-I [8, 22] (Fig.1a). HDGC-related phenotypes accounted for 23.3% (74/317) in Cohort-II truncating carrier families (Fig.3c), representing less than half, as compared to the European counterpart (51.4%; Fig.3a). In truncating carrier families from Cohort-II, the most frequent phenotypes were unspecified GC and UNS-BC (Fig.3c), especially frequent among proband's direct blood relatives (Fig.3c), unlike in Cohort-I, where DGC was predominant in probands (Fig.3a). While LBC was 5.6-fold less frequent than DGC in Cohort-I (Fig.3a), these phenotypes presented similar absolute frequencies (DGC:18 vs LBC:19 cases) in Cohort-II (Fig.3c). In both cohorts, DGC developed before 50yo, but \bar{x} AO was lower in Cohort-II (35.2±15.2yo). Both in America and Europe, LBC was diagnosed generally around 55yo (\bar{x} AO: 55.2±12.5yo and 53.4±17.4yo, respectively). A relevant difference in age of diagnosis was found for GC in relatives, which was higher in Cohort-II (Fig.3c). Other early-onset cancers were very rare in both cohorts (Fig.3a and Fig.3c).

vi. Adaptation of HDGC clinical criteria for CTNNA1 genetic testing can improve the pick-up rate of CTNNA1 truncating variants in HDGC-associated families

The phenotype distribution in truncating carrier families from Cohorts-I and -II highlight geographical specificities, mainly regarding age of cancer onset and reporting of cancer histological classification. This may impact the definition of clinical criteria for *CTNNA1* testing in families/individuals at risk. To address this, we analysed personal/family history and clinical presentations from Cohorts-I and -II, in view of the 'Classic' criteria (C1-C12) [8, 22]. We proposed two new criteria (Fig.3d and Supplementary Table 9) to accommodate the prominence of GC and BC of unknown histology in close relatives of DGC or LBC patients (C13), and the later onset of some HDGC-associated phenotypes (C14) ('*CTNNA1* expanded' criteria). Analysis-B revealed that European and American families were enriched in DGC-centred and LBC-centred criteria, respectively (Fig.3d). Co-occurrence of GC and BC in the same family, with at least one confirmed as DGC or LBC, was similar in European and American families (Fig.3d). Overall, DGC centred familial- and individual-criteria (C1 and C4) accounted for 32% of families, LBC-centred familial- and individual-criteria (C3, C10, C12, C14) for 14.8%, and GC+BC-centred criteria (C2, C11, C13) for 17.3% of all families in Cohorts-I and -II (Supplementary

Tables 9 and 10). Nevertheless, 29 families (29/81; 35.8%) did not comply with any of the abovementioned testing criteria (22% Cohort-I vs. 43% Cohort-II), despite presenting GC and/or BC of unknown histology, some at an early age (Fig.3d and Supplementary Table 9). This highlights the importance of high quality clinical and pathological information to allocate families into relevant clinical criteria for genetic testing. Nevertheless, pathology confirmation is, in some instances, difficult to obtain, which can impair genetic diagnosis and families' clinical management. Direct comparison of HDGC-related phenotypes between Cohorts-I and -II in families meeting the 'Classic + *CTNNA1* expanded' criteria [8, 22] confirmed the predominance of GC, particularly DGC, in Europe, and BC, particularly LBC, in North America (Fig.3e). Combined analysis of European and American families provided a rationale for definition of clinical criteria for *CTNNA1* genetic testing, with relevance for DGC and/or LBC histology confirmation.

vii. A set of clinical criteria driving CTNNA1 genetic testing

The addition of the '*CTNNA1* expanded' to the 'Classic' criteria [8, 22], improved the pick-up rate of *CTNNA1*-associated HDGC by 9% (Supplementary Tables 9 and 10), using a list of 14 items. A parallel set of criteria, the 'Yale' criteria, proposed by Lerner and colleagues [30, 31], focused on personal or family history of GC and adding the NCCN clinical guidelines for high-risk BC [32] (Supplementary Table 10), also comprise 14 items. In both cases, the use of 14 items in clinical practice seems challenging.

To decrease the number of items to consider when identifying families or individuals for *CTNNA1* genetic testing, we propose the 'Porto' criteria (Fig.4a), a simpler set comprising only five topics, that derive from the clinical and molecular findings described above. We tested the performance of the 'Porto' criteria compared to other sets of criteria (Supplementary Table 10), in Cohorts-I, -II and -III. This demonstrated that the 'Porto' criteria (positive predictive value (PPV): 0.91, 95%CI [0.81 – 0.97]; negative predictive value (NPV): 0.20, 95%CI [0.16 – 0.25]) performed equivalently to the 'Classic' [8, 22] and 'Classic + *CTNNA1* expanded' criteria (Fig.4b, Supplementary Tables 10 and 11). Furthermore, the 'Porto' criteria was superior at detecting true negative cases compared to the 'Yale' criteria [30] ('Yale' specificity: 0.65, 95%CI [0.52 – 0.76]; 'Porto' specificity: 0.92, 95%CI [0.83 – 0.97]; $p < 0.0001$). While the 'Porto' criteria presented a significantly lower positive detection rate compared to the 'Yale' criteria ('Yale' sensitivity: 0.52, 95%CI [0.46 – 0.58]; 'Porto' sensitivity: 0.18, 95%CI [0.14 – 0.23]; $p = 0.0002$) (Fig.4b, Supplementary Tables 10 and 11), in absolute numbers, 'Porto' criteria identified 52 families bearing *CTNNA1* truncating variants, all with HDGC-related phenotypes, while

the 'Yale' criteria identified 150 families with truncating variants, but only 46 out of these 150 were diagnosed with either DGC, LBC, or GC of unknown histotype.

viii. CTNNA1-truncating variants present a moderate risk for DGC development

So far, we demonstrated that *CTNNA1*-truncating variants associate with DGC, and recurrently occur in LBC. Still, even with HDGC-suspicion, 35.8% of families did not meet the 'Porto' criteria (Supplementary Table 9). Furthermore, 205 families carrying truncating *CTNNA1* variants and lacking HDGC phenotypes were also reported to the present study (Cohort-III; Fig.1a and Supplementary Tables 2 and 3). The information from Cohorts-I, -II and -III was combined to assess the frequency of families fulfilling the 'Porto' criteria among all families carrying the same truncating variant (Supplementary Table 10). From the TOP12 truncating variants, nine occurred concomitantly in families with and without 'Porto' criteria, while three occur exclusively in families without criteria (Fig.4c). At least 30% of families carrying the c.1351C>T, c.385C>T and c.1991dup variants, and 75% carrying the c.80_81del variant, fulfil the 'Porto' criteria. The latter was found exclusively in European families. More than 80% of families carrying seven different TOP12 recurrent variants (c.105+1G>C, c.2023C>T, c.2191C>T, c.361C>T, c.1969C>T and c.1899.1G>C variants) lack HDGC criteria (Fig.4c).

To understand if *CTNNA1* behaves as a moderate-penetrance gene for HDGC, we conducted Analysis-C, by comparing clinical data from *CTNNA1* truncating carriers with data from carriers of P/LP variants in the classical HDGC gene, *CDH1*. This retrospective analysis specifically assessed the occurrence of HDGC-related cancers in *CTNNA1*- and *CDH1*- variant carriers from 38,112 individuals ascertained based on personal or family history of any cancer (Fig.4d; Supplementary Table 4). From 270 *CTNNA1*-truncating carriers, 2.6% had unspecified GC (7/270; $\bar{x}AO=47.2yo$) and 3.7% had LBC (10/270; $\bar{x}AO=57.4yo$) (Supplementary Table 4). Compared to 37,428 *CTNNA1* and *CDH1* WT individuals, *CTNNA1*-truncating variant carriers were 7.0-fold more likely to develop unspecified GC (OR=7.0; 95%CI [2.9-14.1]; $p<0.00001$), while LBC did not show statistical significance (OR=1.2; 95%CI [0.59-2.15]; $p=0.8900$). Among 414 *CDH1* carriers, the likelihood of GC and LBC development was 37.5-fold and 9.6-fold higher compared to WT individuals (GC: 15.9% (66/414); $\bar{x}AO=42.9yo$; 95%CI [26.7-52.3]; $p<0.00001$; LBC: 19.6% (81/414); $\bar{x}AO=50.5yo$; 95%CI [7.36-12.46]; $p<0.00001$) (Fig.4d). Overall, *CTNNA1*-truncating variant carriers have 5-fold and 8-fold lower risk of developing GC and LBC, respectively, compared to *CDH1* P/LP variant carriers.

Altogether, these results consolidate the risk of GC in *CTNNA1*-truncating variant carriers. Furthermore, as compared to *CDH1*-truncating variants, *CTNNA1*-truncated alleles behave as moderate risk factors predisposing to HDGC.

Figure 4. Evaluation of performance of different HDGC clinical criteria sets, Top 12 most recurrent *CTNNA1* truncating variants in cohort-I, -II and -III and likelihood of cancer development in unselected clinical cohorts. (a) Table depicting the Porto criteria; (b) Forest plot and descriptive table representing the equivalence test for the comparison of ‘Porto’ criteria with other sets of HDGC criteria for *CTNNA1* genetic testing. The equivalence limit (δ) was set to 0.12; (c) Top 12 most recurrent *CTNNA1* truncating variants from 351 carrier families (in red are families meeting the Porto HDGC criteria, in blue are non-HDGC families); (d) Likelihood of GC or LBC development in carriers of truncating *CTNNA1* variants or (likely) pathogenic *CDH1* variants when compared to individuals confirmed to be WT for *CTNNA1* and *CDH1* (individuals were identified in a retrospective cohort by multigene panel testing; carriers of pathogenic and likely pathogenic *CDH1* variants were used for likelihood comparison). Statistically significant results were established by logistic regression models adjusted for age, sex, and self-reported ethnicity ($p < 0.05$). PPV – positive predictive value; NPV – negative predictive value; LBC – lobular breast cancer; GC – gastric cancer unspecified histotype; CI – confidence interval.

ix. CTNNA1-truncating variant carriers are unlikely to develop cancers besides the HDGC-related

To identify additional genotype-phenotype associations in *CTNNA1* beyond HDGC, we analysed families not meeting the 'Porto' criteria from Cohort-I, -II, and -III (Analysis-D) (Fig.1a). This encompassed data from 295 *CTNNA1*-variant carrier families (960 individuals; 1099 disease phenotypes), from which 79.3% (234/295) carried truncating variants. Disease phenotypes were stratified and clustered as "OTHER" when frequency was <2%. MDPT2, Familial Exudative Vitreoretinopathy and Vitelliform macular dystrophy were clustered as Eye Disorders (Fig.5a; Supplementary Table 12). UNS-BC was the most prevalent phenotype in both truncating and non-truncating, with lower \bar{x} AO in non-truncating families (55.0 \pm 13.1yo vs 49.4 \pm 11.9yo) (Fig.5b). Eye disorders were highly frequent in non-truncating carriers (19%) (Fig.5b). Most non-HDGC cancer phenotypes occurred later in life, did not display an enrichment in either truncating or non-truncating families, and were consistently more frequent in relatives with unknown carrier status (Fig.5b). Multivariate logistic regression analysis reinforced the increased likelihood for development of eye disorders in non-truncating carriers (OR=65.64; 95%CI [23.57-250.04]; p <0.0001) (Fig.5c), particularly MDPT2 (Fig.3a). A modest likelihood of OC development in non-truncating carriers was also observed (OR=2.58; 95%CI [1.18-5.33]; p =0.0180) (Fig.5c), still, significance was lost when only confirmed carriers were analysed (Supplementary Table 13).

x. Locus specific genotype-phenotype correlations

We calculated the Pearson correlation for the three major α E-catenin protein domains to find disease-associated hotspots (adherens junctions (AJ), middle fragment (M-Fragment) or actin cytoskeleton binding domains (AC); Cohorts-I, -II and -III). *CTNNA1* last exon was considered NMD-incompetent (Supplementary Fig.3). No strong associations were found for DGC and α E-catenin functional domains, suggesting that the whole gene is a target for HDGC-causing variants. A positive association was found between non-truncating variants and the M-fragment domain (r =0.62; n =32 phenotypes) (Supplementary Fig.3), supporting a clear hotspot in *CTNNA1* and a genotype-phenotype association between non-truncating variants and eye disorders. All other positive associations either display small sample size (n <10 phenotypes) and/or weak Pearson correlation coefficient (r <0.20), imposing a possible bias.

Figure 5. Genotype-phenotype association in individuals/families carrying germline *CTNNA1* variants and not meeting the 'Porto' criteria. (a) frequency analysis of phenotypes in families from Cohorts-I, -II and -III not meeting the 'Porto' criteria, to define a cut-off level for

phenotype analysis (all phenotypes with a frequency lower than 2% were included in OTHER category); (b) genotype-phenotype analysis in families not meeting the 'Porto' criteria from Cohorts-I, -II and -III; families were grouped as carriers of *CTNNA1* variants predicted to cause truncation (truncating) or not (non-truncating) of α E-catenin; (c) Multivariable Firth's bias-reduced penalized-likelihood logistic regression analysis in families not meeting the 'Porto' criteria from Cohorts-I, -II and -III (Truncating vs Non-truncating); this analysis was used to determine the likelihood of phenotype development in Truncating vs Non-truncating variant carriers ($p < 0.05$). HDGC – hereditary diffuse gastric cancer; DGC – diffuse gastric cancer; GC – gastric cancer unspecified histotype; UNS-BC – breast cancer unspecified histotype; CRC – colorectal cancer; OC – ovarian cancer; PC – prostate cancer; LC – lung cancer; PCC – pancreatic cancer; SKC – skin cancer (non-melanoma); MEL – melanoma; EYE D. – noncancerous eye disorders (includes macular dystrophy patterned 2 (MDPT2), familial exudative vitreoretinopathy (FEVR) and vitelliform macular degeneration (VMD)); BRC – Brain cancer; LEU – Leukaemia; KC – Kidney cancer; ThC – Thyroid Cancer; LYMP – Lymphoma; CXC – Cervical cancer; BNC – Bone cancer; LVC – Liver cancer; UtC – Uterine cancer; BDC – Bladder cancer; MMYE – Multiple Myeloma; TrC – Throat Cancer; OEC – Oesophageal cancer; TsC – Testicular cancer; GyC – Gynaecologic cancer; AxC – Appendix cancer; GBC – Gallbladder cancer; H&N – Head and neck cancer; MG – Multinodular goiter; POLYP – Polyposis; SARC – Sarcoma; AC – Abdominal cancer; ACC – Adrenal cancer; EYC – Eye Cancer; VC – Vulvar Cancer; ANC – Anal Cancer; CLP – Cleft lip/palate; EC – Endometrial cancer; EPE – Epileptic encephalopathy; GIST – Gastrointestinal stromal tumor; HYP – Hypodontia; KS – Kaposi sarcoma; MDS – Myelodysplastic syndromes; MEC – Mucoepidermoid carcinoma; MIC – Microdontia; NT – Neuroendocrine tumor; PEC – Peritoneal carcinosis; PPSC – Primary peritoneal serous carcinoma; UrC – Urothelial cancer; GIC – Gastrointestinal carcinoma; LRYC – Laryngeal cancer; OrC – Oral Cancer; UNK – Unknown disease status/Unknown primary Unknown; SD – standard deviation; P – proband; R – 1st or 2nd blood relative (3rd or higher when carrier status is confirmed); CI – confidence interval.

Discussion

CTNNA1 was recognized as a HDGC predisposing gene in 2020 [22], despite the scarce supporting research at that time. Since then, joint efforts have been made to improve knowledge on *CTNNA1* associated disease and cancer lifetime risks [11, 14, 33], however *CTNNA1*-related disease spectrum, variant-type causality and clinical criteria driving genetic testing remain vastly understudied. This knowledge gap hampers defining the best suited clinical management for *CTNNA1*-variant carrier families and the definition of criteria for variant classification.

Here, we report the first study integrating molecular, clinical, population and functional data from a large dataset of germline *CTNNA1* variant carriers. We followed a stepwise approach using different *CTNNA1* variant carrier cohorts to test the association of germline *CTNNA1* variants with disease phenotypes. We demonstrated that early onset DGC is the most frequent phenotype among HDGC families carrying *CTNNA1*-truncating variants, while LBC was less frequent, but recurrent across carriers. The same analysis confirmed *CTNNA1* non-truncating variants as a MDPT2-driver mechanism, consolidating the suspicion of two hereditary syndromes associated with distinct mechanisms of disease [11, 12, 14, 16, 19]. As no family was so far described with both

syndromes, it reinforces the variant-type causality associated with different disease-causing mechanisms.

Although former clinical data suggested that *CTNNA1*-truncating variants are the most likely cancer predisposing factor, the pathophysiological mechanism in *CTNNA1* carrier families remained unproven. We demonstrate, for the first time, that NMD degrades *CTNNA1* transcripts bearing a PTC before *CTNNA1* last exon, where NMD-competent region is thought to reside [28], as we have previously shown for *CDH1*, the classical HDGC gene [26]. Additionally, we consolidate earlier findings, supporting that DGCs from *CTNNA1*-truncating variant carriers lose α E-catenin expression [10, 11, 15]. Our humanized *Drosophila* model also supports these results, as the expression of a PTC-bearing *CTNNA1* cannot rescue *Drosophila* α E-catenin function, leading to impaired organ development and severely impacted adults' survival. Importantly, the *Drosophila* model also showed that missense variants behaved similarly to WT. These *in vitro* and *in vivo* models hold significant importance for clinical practice, particularly to assess functional parameters relevant for *CTNNA1* variants classification. Currently, there are no specific *CTNNA1* variant classification rules, being *CTNNA1* variants classified using the general ACMG/AMP variant classification guidelines [34, 35]. Development of future *CTNNA1* variant classification guidelines will directly benefit from these findings.

These results created the rationale to address, for the first time, genotype-phenotype correlations in families carrying either *CTNNA1*-truncating or non-truncating germline variants. Here, we demonstrate that carriers of truncating variants are 8-fold more likely to develop DGC compared to non-truncating variants carriers. We further show that this still holds true for GC development when compared to *CTNNA1* WT individuals. However, comparing to the likelihood of GC development in *CDH1* truncating variant carriers, we reckon that *CTNNA1* carriers present a lower likelihood of GC development. Although current data is not sufficient to formally link LBC to the *CTNNA1*-associated HDGC spectrum, confirmed carriers of truncating variants from HDGC families are often found to develop LBC, mainly in families with GC or DGC, and particularly in the American cohort. Furthermore, Groot et al. 2018 demonstrated that loss of α E-catenin expression in both mouse and human BC cells correlated with development of lobular and mixed-BC, with invasive behaviour [36]. The small number of LBC cases in the present study may relate with the lack of histopathological evaluation in a high number of early-onset UNS-BC, as well as the overall lower risk associated with the *CTNNA1* gene.

We further understood that a large proportion of *CTNNA1*-truncating carrier families, often carrying recurrent variants, do not fulfil the Porto HDGC criteria, highlighting *CTNNA1* as a moderate penetrance gene for HDGC. This knowledge is pivotal to improve the clinical pathway of care for carriers of *CTNNA1*-truncating variants. Moderate penetrance genes are particularly challenging in the clinics, since the increased risk for cancer development may not justify prophylactic measures as severe as those used in the context of high penetrance genes [37]. Thus, we believe that any upcoming HDGC clinical recommendations should reflect the differences in cancer risks for *CDH1* and *CTNNA1*. To this day, only one study has been reported analysing the life-time risk of developing DGC in *CTNNA1* variant carriers [33], from families meeting HDGC criteria [22], where carriers presented ~50% increased risk of developing DGC by age 80. This is similar to earlier reports of DGC life-time risks in *CDH1* carriers [13, 38-40], which ranged from 37% to 70% in men and 25% to 83% in women. A recent study by Ryan et. al. 2024 [41] showed that the risk for developing DGC is significantly smaller (~10% by age 80) in a cohort of 7,323 carrier individuals, pinpointing that, even for *CDH1*, the risk of developing DGC has been overestimated [41]. Nevertheless, the risk increases to 38% in carriers with an enriched GC family history. With the currently available *CTNNA1* germline data, we cannot guarantee that the probability of developing cancer in a truncating *CTNNA1* variant carrier depends only on cancer family history. Most likely, this likelihood depends not only on these two factors but also on others yet to be discovered, such as environmental players and/or genetic/epigenetic modifiers [42]. Overall, our results suggest that the pathway of care of *CTNNA1*-truncating variant carrier' families should consider and adapt according to the presence or absence of HDGC-related phenotypes. Furthermore, expanding *CTNNA1* genetic testing in the context of DGC and/or LBC may be beneficial, since more carriers will be genetically diagnosed and properly referred for adequate clinical care. This rationale led us to integrate the clinical, molecular and functional data from cohorts of different geographical origins, which provided important input regarding the adaptation of HDGC clinical criteria for *CTNNA1* germline testing. Herein, we present a set of HDGC criteria for *CTNNA1* genetic testing that is simpler than any other HDGC clinical criteria for genetic testing [8, 22, 30]. The 'Porto' criteria evolved from other HDGC sets of clinical criteria [8, 22, 30], summarizes into five criteria most clinical presentations expected to occur in individuals or families carrying a *CTNNA1*-truncating variant, without affecting their global performance, and outperforming the specificity of the very sensitive Yale criteria [30]. These data indicates that the outcomes of *CTNNA1* genetic testing will be improved by the application of the 'Porto' criteria.

Although the proposed criteria seem reasonable to drive *CTNNA1* genetic testing based on the present data, 29 (36%) families in Analysis-B fail to fulfil the 'Porto' criteria, from which most presented GC and BC without confirmed histology. The lack of histology confirmation prevents recognition of individuals and families for *CTNNA1* testing, impacting the rationale for cascade testing in relatives and engagement in HDGC-related clinical management [22, 43-45]. The importance of BC histology is highlighted by 8/29 families which meet a BC-centred 'Yale' criteria inspired by the NCCN guidelines, but for which there is no evidence of association with truncating *CTNNA1* variants. Revisiting the pathology of these tumours may inform on the LBC patients fraction that may be eligible for *CTNNA1*-related clinical management. However, we acknowledge that potential harm may occur if families with GC and/or BC, lacking pathology confirmation, remain untested, and are later proven to carry a *CTNNA1* variant or other cancer predisposing variant. Given that we herein demonstrate that *CTNNA1* is a moderate penetrance gene, as compared to *CDH1*, and that the *CDH1*-associated DGC and LBC are very rare diseases, the number of *CTNNA1* positive genetic diagnosis, among GC or BC families overall, is likely extremely low.

Many families carrying *CTNNA1* germline variants reported to us also developed HDGC-unrelated phenotypes, as illustrated by Cohort-III. This suggests that the cancer spectrum in *CTNNA1*-truncating variant carriers may depend on additional genetic or environmental events [46-48]. Nevertheless, no other strong associations were found between *CTNNA1*-truncating variants and other cancer types. Also, no cancer phenotypes displayed a strong association with a specific protein domain, which reinforced loss of *CTNNA1* expression as the mechanism behind HDGC development. We further show, for the first time, a positive association of *CTNNA1* non-truncating variants in the M-fragment domain to eye disorders, especially MDPT2. It has been demonstrated that this protein region is a regulatory domain, responsible for the binding and interaction with several different proteins [2, 49, 50]. Thus, it is likely that alterations of specific amino acids in this domain may change the protein conformation, impairing α E-catenin proper binding to other proteins, with particular relevance in the eye.

Our study reveals important limitations to be considered, some of them inherent to geography-related clinical practice. In Europe, genetic testing is generally driven by clinical suspicion, and gene panels are often adjusted according to family and/or personal clinical presentation, as only in such cases the cost of the test is covered by the National Health systems or health insurances. In USA, multigene cancer panels are often large, containing numerous cancer risk genes that may not be consistent with or

expected in patients or families' phenotype context. Additionally, while clinical suspicion according to guidelines drive genetic testing in both world regions, mainly in the hospital setting, in North America there are higher rates of multigene panel testing outside of guideline recommendations, with American patients more frequently paying for testing out-of-pocket. Furthermore, the retrospective nature of large data collection can introduce a potential bias. The incomplete family histories, inconsistent phenotypic data reporting, or the recruitment nature of each family across different geographical regions (mainly based on strict clinical criteria in Europe and obtained from large genetic testing laboratories in North America) can result in a non-neglectable ascertainment bias. To circumvent this, we analysed Cohort-I (European) first to establish genotype-phenotype associations and variant type-causality, and then validate results in an independent American cohort (Cohort-II) enriched in HDGC-related phenotypes. This analysis confirmed the *CTNNA1*-associated disease spectrum, while highlighting important differences in DGC and LBC frequencies in families carrying *CTNNA1*-truncating variants, which we have also seen in *CDH1*-associated families [8]. Furthermore, the unequal sample sizes of phenotypes in truncating and non-truncating variant carriers in Cohort-III, may reduce the strength of phenotype associations with different protein domains, and additional cancer types. Although a thorough review of family's pedigrees and clinical data was conducted for recurrent variants to remove duplicated families, we cannot completely exclude duplication issues.

In conclusion, our study formally demonstrates a link between *CTNNA1*-truncating variants and DGC development, with NMD emerging as the key first hit mechanism driving *CTNNA1* LoF in the germline. Although less obvious, the recurrent occurrence of LBC in truncating variant carrier families, often combined with DGC, claims for the inclusion of LBC in the *CTNNA1*-associated disease spectrum. We also consolidated earlier evidence for the risk of MDPT2 in carriers of non-truncating variants, showing for the first time that MDPT2-associated variants cluster in the α E-catenin M-fragment domain. Lastly, we show that *CTNNA1* is a moderate penetrance gene in HDGC, when compared to *CDH1*, with impact for the design of clinical recommendations for *CTNNA1*-truncating variant carriers. In light of the results here presented, large scale studies are required to assess, quantitatively, the lifetime cancer risk in *CTNNA1* truncating variant carriers, as well as to consolidate the *CTNNA1*-associated disease spectrum.

This study fills the gap in knowledge on *CTNNA1*-related predisposition, adding *CTNNA1* as a *bona-fide* and moderate penetrance gene in HDGC, and proposing clinical criteria driving *CTNNA1* genetic testing. Given the difference in cancer risk for *CTNNA1*, in

comparison to *CDH1*, we believe that clinical management should be adapted. Our findings underscore the importance of integrating *CTNNA1* genetic testing results with family and personal histories of DGC and LBC, particularly when considering prophylactic interventions for variant carriers across diverse populations.

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Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1. Schematic description of individuals and families included in the current study (Cohort-I, -II and -III). Data is represented per continent where patients and families received care. ‘Study collaborators’ refers to data on families/individuals obtained from collaborators of the present study, while ‘Previous publications’ refers to data on families/individuals retrieved from scientific publication. ‘HDGC’ comprises all families with a personal and/or family history of DGC, GC and/or LBC, or any combination of DGC or LBC with GC. ‘Non-HDGC’ comprises all individuals or families not meeting the former ‘HDGC’ definition. ‘Eye disorders’ refers to families or individuals presenting personal and/or family history of macular dystrophy patterned 2, familial exudative vitreoretinopathy and/or vitelliform macular degeneration. None of the eye disorder families were reported to present HDGC phenotypes. ‘Families from other origins’ comprises three families from Asia. HDGC – hereditary diffuse gastric cancer.

Supplementary Figure 2. Characterization of the MKN74 isogenic cell line *CTNNA1*_EX11Del, genetically edited by CRISPR/Cas9 to delete *CTNNA1* out-of-frame exon 11. (a) Analysis on the mRNA expression of *CTNNA1* in WT and *CTNNA1*_EX11Del MKN74 cells. P1 and P2 comprise two qPCR probes: P1 – targeting exons 3-4 (Hs.PT.58.14970051); P2 – targeting exon 13-14 (Hs.PT.58.787439); Analysis on αE-catenin protein expression by (b) flow cytometry and (c) immunofluorescence. αE-catenin is represented in red, GFP in green and DAPI in blue. White scale bars represent a distance of 25μm. Statistically significant results were established by two-tailed paired t-test (* p < 0.05; ** p < 0.01; *** p < 0.001; **** p < 0.0001).

Supplementary Figure 3. Locus specific genotype-phenotype correlations in disease phenotypes from Cohorts-I, -II and -III. Pearson correlation was calculated to assess any possible positive correlations between specific protein regions and disease phenotypes (n=1181 and 176 disease phenotypes in truncating and non-truncating variant carrier groups, respectively; p<0.05). A significant and robust positive correlation was considered when Pearson's coefficient was >0.5 and n>10 phenotypes. DGC – diffuse gastric cancer; GC – gastric cancer unspecified histotype; LBC – lobular breast cancer; UNS-BC – breast cancer unspecified histotype; CRC – colorectal cancer; OC – ovarian cancer; PC – prostate cancer; LC – lung cancer; PCC – pancreatic cancer; SKC – skin cancer (non-melanoma); MEL – melanoma; EYE D. – non cancerous eye disorders (includes macular dystrophy patterned 2 (MDPT2), familial exudative vitreoretinopathy (FEVR) and vitelliform macular degeneration (VMD)); OTHER – other disease phenotypes not in the above mentioned; NMD – nonsense mediated mRNA decay.

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1: Database contributions of families carrying rare *CTNNA1* germline variants by affiliation and country.

Institution of submitting authors	Country	No. of families referred per Country	Continent	No. of families referred per continent		
Groupe Hospitalier Pitié-Salpêtrière, Paris, France; Hôpital Saint-Antoine, AP-HP, Paris, France	France	6	Europe	86		
Institut Curie, University Paris Sciences Lettres, Paris, France	France					
Nantes University Hospital, Nantes	France					
University Hospital Bonn, Bonn, Germany; Medical Faculty, University of Bonn, Bonn, Germany	Germany	9				
Universitätsklinikum Carl Gustav Carus Dresden, Technischen Universität Dresden, Dresden, Germany	Germany					
IFLb Laboratoriumsmedizin Berlin GmbH, Windscheidstraße, Berlin- Charlottenburg, Germany	Germany					
Medizinische Klinik und Poliklinik IV, Klinikum der Universität München, Munich, Germany; Medizinisch Genetisches Zentrum, Munich, Germany	Germany					
ULSSJ - Unidade Local de Saúde São João, Porto, Portugal	Portugal	5				
ULSC - Unidade Local de Saúde de Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal	Portugal					
Portuguese Oncology Institute of Porto (IPO-Porto), Porto, Portugal	Portugal					
ULSB - Unidade Local de Saúde de Braga, Braga, Portugal	Portugal					
Hospital Clínic Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain; Centro de Investigación Biomédica en Red en Enfermedades Hepáticas y Digestivas, Barcelona, Spain; Institut d'Investigacions Biomèdiques August Pi i Sunyer, University of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain	Spain	61				
Catalan Institute of Oncology, Bellvitge Institute for Biomedical Research, Barcelona, Spain; Centro de Investigación Biomédica en Red de Cáncer, Madrid, Spain	Spain					
Medical Oncology Department Hospital Vall d'Hebron, Vall d'Hebron Institute of Oncology, Barcelona, Spain	Spain					
Hospital Universitario de Cruces, Bizkaia, Spain	Spain					
Universidad de Navarra, Navarra, Spain	Spain					
Amsterdam UMC, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Amsterdam, The Netherlands	The Netherlands		5			
Netherlands Cancer Institute, Amsterdam, The Netherlands	The Netherlands					
Erasmus MC Rotterdam, Rotterdam, The Netherlands	The Netherlands					
Barretos Cancer Hospital, São Paulo, Brazil	Brazil	1	America	257		
Zane Cohen Centre, Sinai Health System, Toronto, Canada	Canada	3				
Faculty of Medicine, University of British Columbia, Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada; BC Cancer, Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada	Canada					
Center for Cancer Research, National Cancer Institute, Maryland, United States	United States of America	253				
AmbryGenetics, California, United States of America	United States of America					
University of Pennsylvania Perelman School of Medicine, Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, United States of America	United States of America					
The University of Texas MD Anderson Cancer Center, Houston, Texas, United States of America	United States of America					
Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center, New York, United States of America	United States of America					
Original setting of the contributed families	Continent	No. of families				
Recruited in the clinics	Europe	33				
	North America	32				
Recruited in clinical diagnostic laboratories	Europe	53				
	North America	225				

Supplementary Table 2. Detailed description of all families included in Cohorts I, II and III

Family_ID	Continent of diagnosis	Cohort-I	Cohort-II	Cohort-III	Nucleotide Change (HGVS)	Protein Change (HGVS)	Protein domain	Molecular classification	Variant predicted consequence	NMD competence region	Premature termination codon	Variant group	Cancer history	GC and/or BC history: Eye disorder history	Relevant disease history (DGC, GC, BC; BC <50 or MDPTZ/FEVR/WMD)	Classic criteria [8, 22]	Classic [8, 22] + C7NMAI expanded criteria	Porto' criteria	Yale criteria	References
F001	North America	No	No	Yes	c.8C>T	p.Ala3Val	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UBS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F002	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.25A>G	p.Ile5Val	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F003	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.46A>G	p.Lys16Glu	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UBS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F004	North America	No	No	Yes	c.68dup	p.Ala24Glyfs*3	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	2 UBS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C14	-
F005	Europe	Yes	No	No	c.80_81del	p.Arg27His*17	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	13 DGC (3 <50); 1 UNS-BC (<50)	C1	C1	C1	C1	10.1002/path.4152
F006	Europe	Yes	No	No	c.80_81del	p.Arg27His*17	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	2 LBC (<50)	C3	C3	C3	C3	-
F007	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.80_81del	p.Arg27His*17	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F008	Europe	Yes	No	No	c.80_81del	p.Arg27His*17	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC-only	1 DGC (<50)	C4	C4	C2	C1	-
F009	North America	No	Yes	No	c.86del	p.Leu29Trpfs*12	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 DGC; 3 UNS-BC (<50)	No	C13	C4	C1	-
F010	North America	No	No	Yes	c.86del	p.Leu29Trpfs*12	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C9	-
F011	North America	No	No	Yes	c.95_96del	p.Leu32Argfs*12	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F012	North America	No	Yes	Yes	c.99del	p.Trh34Hisfs*7	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	GC+BC	2 GC	No	No	No	No	-
F013	North America	No	Yes	No	c.99del	p.Trh34Hisfs*7	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 LBC; 2 GC	C11	C11	C4	No	-
F014	North America	No	No	Yes	c.100dup	p.Trh34Asnfs*11	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	C14	-
F015	North America	No	No	Yes	c.105+1G>C	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	https://doi.org/10.1038/541436-020-0753-1
F016	North America	No	No	Yes	c.105+1G>C	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	No	No	No	C8	https://doi.org/10.1038/541436-020-0753-1
F017	North America	No	Yes	No	c.105+1G>C	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	1 LBC	No	C14	C5	No	https://doi.org/10.1038/541436-020-0753-1
F018	North America	No	No	Yes	c.105+1G>C	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	https://doi.org/10.1038/541436-020-0753-1
F019	North America	No	No	Yes	c.105+1G>C	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F020	North America	No	No	Yes	c.105+1G>C	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	Other	-	No	No	No	C14	-
F021	North America	No	No	Yes	c.105+1G>C	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F022	North America	No	No	Yes	c.105+1G>C	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C14	-

F047	North America	No	No	Yes	c.105+1G>C	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	No	No	No	-
F048	North America	No	No	Yes	c.105+1G>C	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	C3	-
F049	North America	No	No	Yes	c.105+1G>C	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	-	No	No	C14	-
F050	North America	No	No	Yes	c.105+1G>C	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	-
F051	North America	No	No	Yes	c.105+1G>C	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	-
F052	North America	No	Yes	No	c.105+1G>C	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 LBC (<50); 1 UNS-BC (<50)	C10	C3	C3	-
F053	North America	No	Yes	Yes	c.105+1G>C	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	2 GC	No	No	C12	-
F054	North America	No	Yes	No	c.106-2A>C	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC-only	2 DGC (<50)	C1	C1	C1	-
F055	North America	No	No	Yes	c.149_174dup	p.His59Argfs*45	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	C3	-
F056	North America	No	No	Yes	c.151_152del	p.Lys51Glufs*5	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	-	No disease	-	No	No	No	-
F057	North America	No	No	Yes	c.160_161insCT	p.Arg54Profs*42	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	Other	-	No	No	No	-
F058	North America	No	Yes	No	c.160_161insCT	p.Arg54Profs*42	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 DGC (<50)	C4	C2	C1	-
F059	North America	No	No	Yes	c.167dup	p.Lys57Glufs*10	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	-
F060	North America	No	Yes	Yes	c.182T>A	p.Leu61*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 GC (<50)	No	No	C14	-
F061	North America	No	No	Yes	c.195_198del	p.Glu66Lysfs*28	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	-	No disease	-	No	No	No	10.1098/gm.2015.212
F062	Europe	Yes	No	No	c.208G>A	p.Glu70Lys	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familial	GC-only	1 DGC (<50)	C4	C2	C1	-
F063	North America	No	Yes	No	c.211A>AT	p.Asn71Ilefs*8	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC-only	2 DGC (<50)	C1	C1	C1	10.1001/jamaoncol.2014.168
F064	Asia	No	No	Yes	c.215T>C	p.Phe72Ser	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	-	Eye disorders-only	2 FEVR	No	No	No	https://doi.org/10.1172/JCI13986
F065	North America	No	Yes	Yes	c.222_223del	p.Lys75Glyfs*3	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 GC; 1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	9
F066	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.248G>A	p.Ser83Asn	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	-
F067	Europe	Yes	No	No	c.257del	-	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 LBC; 1 DGC (<50)	C4	C4	C1	-
F068	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.292C>T	p.Arg98*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	Other	-	No	No	No	-
F069	North America	No	No	Yes	c.292C>T	p.Arg98*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	-
F070	North America	No	No	Yes	c.292C>T	p.Arg98*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	Other	-	No	No	No	-

F071	North America	No	No	Yes	c.292C>T	p.Arg98*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C14	-
F072	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.293G>A	p.Arg98Gln	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F073	North America	No	No	Yes	c.298C>T	p.Gln100*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	C14	-
F074	North America	No	No	Yes	c.301+1del	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F075	North America	No	No	Yes	c.301+1G>A	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	C7	-
F076	Europe	Yes	No	No	c.303_316del	p.Asp102Cysfs*8	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC-only	1 DGC (<50); 2 GC (1-50)	C1	C1	C1	C1	-
F077	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.316G>A	p.Ala106Thr	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F078	North America	No	Yes	No	c.321dupT	p.Ala108Cysfs*7	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 LBC (<50); 1 GC	C11	C11	C3	-	
F079	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.339T>A	p.Asp113Glu	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F080	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.339T>A	p.Asp113Glu	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F081	North America	No	No	Yes	c.361C>T	p.Arg121*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F082	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.361C>T	p.Arg121*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F083	North America	No	No	Yes	c.361C>T	p.Arg121*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	-	Unknown	-	No	No	No	No	-
F084	North America	No	Yes	Yes	c.361C>T	p.Arg121*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	GC-only	1 GC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F085	North America	No	No	Yes	c.361C>T	p.Arg121*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F086	North America	No	No	Yes	c.361C>T	p.Arg121*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	3 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C14	-
F087	Europe	Yes	No	No	c.385C>T	p.Arg129*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC-only	2 DGC	C1	C1	C1	C1	10.1001/jamaonc ol.2014.168
F088	North America	No	Yes	No	c.385C>T	p.Arg129*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	GC-only	1 DGC (<50)	C4	C4	C2	C1	10.1016/j.cancer gen.2017.08.001
F089	North America	No	Yes	Yes	c.385C>T	p.Arg129*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	GC-only	1 GC	No	No	No	No	-
F090	North America	No	No	Yes	c.385C>T	p.Arg129*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	C14	-
F091	North America	No	No	Yes	c.385C>T	p.Arg129*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F092	North America	No	No	Yes	c.385C>T	p.Arg129*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F093	North America	No	Yes	No	c.385C>T	p.Arg129*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 DGC (<50)	C4	C4	C4	C1	-
F094	North America	No	No	Yes	c.392dup	p.Leu131Phefs*13	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	https://doi.org/10.1038/441436-090-0753-1

F095	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.406dup	p.Trp136Asnfs*8	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C9	-
F096	Europe	Yes	No	No	Yes	c.409C>T	p.Arg137Trp	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	-	No disease	-	No	No	No	No	-
F097	Europe	Yes	No	No	Yes	c.410G>A	p.Arg137Gln	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F098	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.422dup	p.Leu141Phefs*3	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F099	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.468+1G>A	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	https://doi.org/10.1038/44136-020-0753-1
F100	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.468+1G>A	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F101	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.468+1G>C	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F102	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.468+1G>C	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F103	Europe	Yes	No	No	Yes	c.479G>T	p.Gly160Val	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familiar	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F104	North America	No	Yes	No	Yes	c.479dup	p.Ile161Tyrfs*10	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	GC-only	1 GC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F105	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.481A>C	p.Ile161Val	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F106	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.498del	p.Asn166Lysfs*8	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F107	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.520G>T	p.Gly174*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F108	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.526C>T	p.Gln176*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F109	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.526C>T	p.Gln176*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F110	North America	No	Yes	No	Yes	c.527del	p.Gln176Argfs*5	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	GC+BC	1 GC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F111	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.529dup	p.Tyr177Leufs*2	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F112	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.530A>G	p.Tyr177Cys	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F113	Europe	Yes	No	No	No	c.543del	p.Lys181Asnfs*7	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	GC+BC	3 DGC (1<50), 1 UNS-BC	C1	C1	C1	C1	-
F114	Europe	Yes	No	No	Yes	c.563A>G	p.Asn188Ser	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familiar	GC-only	1 DGC (<55)	No	No	No	C1	-
F115	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.577A>T	p.Lys193*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F116	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.588+2T>A	-	Adherens junction binding	Splice-site	Non-coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F117	North America	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	c.607C>T	p.His203Tyr	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal	GC+BC	1 DGC	No	C13	C4	C1	-
F118	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.616C>T	p.Gln206*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-

F119	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.645G>T	p.Gln215His	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F120	North America	No	Yes	No	c.660_666del	p.Tyr222Hisfs*20	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	1 LBC	C10	C10	C3	No	-
F121	North America	No	No	Yes	c.676C>T	p.Gln226*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C14	-
F122	North America	No	No	Yes	c.688C>T	p.Gln230*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F123	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.733T>C	p.Tyr245His	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	3 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F124	North America	No	Yes	No	c.735C>G	p.Tyr245*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 LBC (<55)	C12	C12	C5	C3	-
F125	North America	No	No	Yes	c.770A>T	p.Asn257Ile	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F126	North America	No	No	Yes	c.778C>T	p.Gln260	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C14	-
F127	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.778C>T	p.Gln260*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F128	North America	No	No	Yes	c.781del	p.Ala261Profs*34	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C14	-
F129	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.784A>C	p.Thr262Pro	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F130	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.784A>C	p.Thr262Pro	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F131	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.795C>G	p.Asp265Glu	Adherens junction binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F132	North America	No	No	Yes	c.803C>G	p.Ser268*	Adherens junction binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F133	North America	No	No	Yes	c.805del	p.Gln269Serfs*26	Adherens junction binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F134	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.81E_817Ins GGA	p.Gly276dup	Adherens junction binding	In-frame insertion	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F135	North America	No	No	Yes	c.879del	p.Leu294*	M-fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F136	North America	No	No	Yes	c.892G>T	p.Glu298*	M-fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F137	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.919G>A	p.Glu307Lys	M-fragment	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familial	Eye disorders-only	3 MIDFT2	No	No	No	No	10.1038/ng.3474
F138	North America	No	No	Yes	c.923G>A	p.Arg308His	M-fragment	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F139	North America	No	Yes	No	c.92E_936del	p.Leu309Hisfs*2	M-fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 DGC (<50)	C4	C4	C1	https://doi.org/10.1038/541436-020-0753-1	
F140	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.953T>C	p.Leu318Ser	M-fragment	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	-	Eye disorders-only	9 MIDFT2	No	No	No	No	10.1038/ng.3474
F141	Europe	Yes	No	No	c.964_988dup	p.Arg330Leufs*6	M-fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 DGC (<50); 1 GC (<50); 1 LBC	C1	C1	C1	10.1136/jmedgenet-2017-104962	
F142	North America	No	No	Yes	c.964_988dup	p.Arg330Leufs*6	M-fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F143	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.965C>T	p.Ser322Leu	M-fragment	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	-	Eye disorders-only	3 MIDFT2	No	No	No	No	10.1016/j.ophtha.2020.10.032
F144	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.965C>T	p.Ser322Leu	M-fragment	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	-	Eye disorders-only	2 MIDFT2	No	No	No	No	10.1016/j.ophtha.2020.10.032

F145	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.973A>G	p.Thr325Ala	M-Fragment	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	-	Eye disorders-only	1.MDPT2	No	No	No	No	10.1016/j.ophtha.2020.10.032
F146	North America	No	No	Yes	c.994C>T	p.Arg332*	M-Fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F147	North America	No	No	Yes	c.994C>T	p.Arg332*	M-Fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F148	North America	No	No	Yes	c.994C>T	p.Arg332*	M-Fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F149	North America	No	No	Yes	c.994C>T	p.Arg332*	M-Fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F150	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1006del	p.Glu336Serfs* ₃₃	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C14	-
F151	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1024C>T	p.Gln342*	M-Fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC+Eye Disorders	1 VMD	No	No	No	No	-
F152	Europe	Yes	No	No	c.1030del	p.Leu344Cysfs* ₂₅	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 DGC (<50)	C4	C4	C2	C1	-
F153	North America	No	Yes	No	c.1033C>T	p.Gln345*	M-Fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 LBC; 1 GC	C11	C11	C3	C5	-
F154	North America	No	Yes	Yes	c.1041dup	p.Leu348Alafs* ₁₁	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 GC	No	No	No	C5	-
F155	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1063-1G>A	-	M-Fragment	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F156	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1063-1G>A	-	M-Fragment	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F157	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1072_1075del	p.Arg360Valfs* ₈	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	Other	-	No	No	No	No	10.1016/j.ophtha.2019.11.009
F158	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1078_1081del	p.Arg360Valfs* ₈	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	https://doi.org/10.1038/441436-020-0753-1
F159	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1078_1081del	p.Arg360Valfs* ₈	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F160	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1078_1081del	p.Arg360Valfs* ₈	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F161	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1078_1081del	p.Arg360Valfs* ₈	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C9	-
F162	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1117A>T	p.Lys373*	M-Fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F163	Asia	No	No	Yes	c.1125_1131del	p.Arg376Cysfs* ₂₇	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	-	Eye disorders-only	2 FEVR	No	No	No	No	10.1172/JCI139869
F164	North America	No	Yes	Yes	c.1126A>T	p.Arg376Trp	M-Fragment	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familial	GC-only	1 GC	No	No	No	No	-
F165	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1134dup	p.Arg379Alafs* ₂	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F166	Europe	Yes	No	No	c.1175del	p.Asp392Valfs* ₁₃	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC-only	2 DGC (<50)	C1	C1	C1	C1	-
F167	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1181dup	p.Leu395Profs* ₁₂	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F168	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.1192A>G	p.Asn398Asp	M-Fragment	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F169	North America	No	Yes	No	c.1205del	p.Leu402Trps* ₃	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 DGC	No	C13	C4	C1	-
F170	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.1207G>A	p.Val403Ile	M-Fragment	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F171	South America	No	No	Yes	c.1207delinsCT	p.Val403Profs* ₃	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F172	North America	No	Yes	No	c.1246_1248del	p.Val416Argfs* ₁₄	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 LBC (<50); 1 GC; 1 UNS-BC (<50)	C10	C10	C3	C3	-
F173	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1246_1248del	p.Val416Argfs* ₁₄	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F174	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1246_1294del	p.Val416Argfs* ₁₆	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	https://doi.org/10.1038/441436-020-0753-1
F175	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1261C>T	p.Gln421*	M-Fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	https://doi.org/10.1038/441436-020-0753-1
F176	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.1271G>A	p.Arg424His	M-Fragment	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F177	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1292_1295del	p.Ile431Argfs* ₁₆	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	C8	-

F178	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1292_1295del	p.Ile431Argfs*16	M-fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial/multifactorial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F179	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1292_1295del	p.Ile431Argfs*16	M-fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C9	-
F180	North America	No	Yes	No	c.1292_1295del	p.Ile431Argfs*16	M-fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	3 LBC; 1 GC; 1 UNS-BC (<50)	C10	C10	C3	-	
F181	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1292_1295del	p.Ile431Argfs*16	M-fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F182	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.1293T>G	p.Ile431Met	M-fragment	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	-	Eye disorders-only	2 MIDPTZ	No	No	No	No	10.1039/ng.3474
F183	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.1294G>A	p.Glu432Lys	M-fragment	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	-	Eye disorders-only	1 MIDPTZ	No	No	No	No	10.1016/j.ophtha.2020.10.032
F184	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.1316C>T	p.Ser439Phe	M-fragment	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	-	Eye disorders-only	4 MIDPTZ	No	No	No	No	10.1016/j.ophtha.2020.10.032
F185	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.1316C>T	p.Ser439Phe	M-fragment	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	-	Eye disorders-only	3 MIDPTZ	No	No	No	No	10.1016/j.ophtha.2020.10.032
F186	Europe	Yes	No	No	c.1328dup	p.Asn443Lysfs*2	M-fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC-only	1 DGC (<50); 1 GC (<50)	C1	C1	C1	C1	10.1136/j.medgen.2017.104962
F187	Europe	Yes	No	No	c.1329del	p.Asn443Lysfs*5	M-fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC-only	1 DGC (<50)	C4	C4	C2	C1	-
F188	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1330dup	p.Glu446Glyfs*23	M-fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	https://doi.org/10.1038/41436-020-0753-1
F189	North America	No	Yes	No	c.1351C>T	p.Arg451*	M-fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	2 DGC (1<50); 1 LBC	C2	C2	C1	C1	https://doi.org/10.1038/41436-020-0753-1
F190	North America	No	Yes	No	c.1351C>T	p.Arg451*	M-fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC-only	1 DGC (<50); 1 GC (<50)	C1	C1	C1	C1	https://doi.org/10.1038/41436-020-0753-1
F191	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1351C>T	p.Arg451*	M-fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	C12	https://doi.org/10.1038/41436-020-0753-1
F192	North America	No	Yes	No	c.1351C>T	p.Arg451*	M-fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 LBC (<50)	C12	C12	C5	C3	-
F193	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1351C>T	p.Arg451*	M-fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F194	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1351C>T	p.Arg451*	M-fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F195	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1351C>T	p.Arg451*	M-fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F196	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1351C>T	p.Arg451*	M-fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F197	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1351C>T	p.Arg451*	M-fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F198	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1371_1381dup	p.Cys461*	M-fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F199	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1390-2A>C	-	M-fragment	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	-	Unknown	-	No	No	No	No	-
F200	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1390-2A>C	-	M-fragment	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F201	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1393A>G	p.Ile465Val	M-fragment	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F202	North America	No	Yes	Yes	c.1412T>A	p.Leu471*	M-fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	GC-only	1 GC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F203	Europe	Yes	No	No	c.1426C>T	p.Gln476*	M-fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC-only	1 DGC (<50); 1 GC	C1	C1	C1	C1	10.3390/cancers15174313
F204	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.1450A>G	p.Met484Val	M-fragment	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F205	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1451T>C	p.Met484Thr	M-fragment	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F206	North America	No	Yes	Yes	c.1461dup	p.Lys488*	M-fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 UNS-BC (<50); 1 GC (>50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F207	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1461dup	p.Lys488*	M-fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F208	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1479del	p.Lys493Asnfs*31	M-fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F209	Europe	Yes	No	No	c.1544C>G	p.Ser515*	M-fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC-only	2 DGC (1<50); 1 GC (<50)	C1	C1	C1	C1	-

F210	Europe	No	Yes	No	No	c.1544C>G	p.Ser515*	M-Fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	GC+BC	1 LBC (<50); 1 DGC (<50)	C2	C2	C3	C1	-
F211	Europe	No	Yes	No	No	c.1608dup	p.Gly577Trpfs* 28	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	GC-only	1 DGC (<50)	C4	C4	C2	C1	-
F212	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.1613_1617dup	p.Arg540Trpfs* 18	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	https://doi.org/10.1038/41436-020-0753-1
F213	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.1613_1617dup	p.Arg540Trpfs* 18	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	No
F214	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.1617C>A	p.Asp396Glu	M-Fragment	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F215	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.1636C>T	p.Arg546*	M-Fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	Unknown	-	No	No	No	C11	-
F216	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.1745_1746insTGGAA	p.Val583Glyfs* 11	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	-	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F217	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.1768C>T	p.Gln590*	M-Fragment	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F218	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.1779del	p.Ala594Profs* 37	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F219	Europe	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	c.1829_1830msA	p.Phe611fs*10	M-Fragment	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F220	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.1853dup	p.Tyr619Ilefs*2	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F221	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.1870dup	p.Asp624Glyfs* 13	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	-	No	No	No	C11	-
F222	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.1899+1G>C	-	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F223	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.1899+1G>C	-	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F224	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.1899+1G>C	-	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F225	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.1899+1G>C	-	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	-	No	No	No	C11	-
F226	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.1899+1G>C	-	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Splice-site	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C14	-
F227	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.1932_1953dup	p.Ser652Aspfs* 5	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C9	-
F228	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.1936_1937del	p.Glu646Argfs* 3	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F229	North America	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	c.1966G>A	p.Val656Ile	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familiar	GC-only	2 GC	No	No	No	No	-
F230	North America	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	c.1969C>T	p.Gln657*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	GC+BC	1 GC; 1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C9	-
F231	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.1969C>T	p.Gln657*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F232	North America	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	c.1969C>T	p.Gln657*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	GC+BC	1 GC	No	No	No	No	-
F233	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.1969C>T	p.Gln657*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	-	No	No	No	C14	-
F234	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.1969C>T	p.Gln657*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	C14	-
F235	North America	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	c.1969C>T	p.Gln657*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	GC+BC	1 GC; 1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F236	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.1981_1982del	p.Asp651Serfs* 40	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-

F237	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1991dup	p.Ala665Serfs* 37	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	C3	-
F238	North America	No	Yes	No	c.1991dup	p.Ala665Serfs* 37	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	GC-only	1 DGC (<50)	C4	C2	C1	-
F239	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1991dup	p.Ala665Serfs* 37	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	-
F240	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1991dup	p.Ala665Serfs* 37	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	C9	-
F241	North America	No	Yes	No	c.1991dup	p.Ala665Serfs* 37	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 DGC (<55)	No	C4	C1	-
F242	North America	No	Yes	No	c.1997del	p.Gly666Alafs* 56	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	GC-only	1 DGC (<50)	C4	C2	C1	https://doi.org/10.1038/441436-020-0753-1
F243	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1997del	p.Gly666Alafs* 56	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	-	No	No	C14	-
F244	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1997del	p.Gly666Alafs* 56	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	Other	-	No	No	No	-
F245	North America	No	No	Yes	c.1997del	p.Gly666Alafs* 56	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	C3	-
F246	North America	No	No	Yes	c.2010+2_2010-3insC	-	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Splice-site/intronic variant	Non-coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	Familial	Other	-	No	No	No	-
F247	Europe	Yes	No	No	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	5 DGC (4<50); 2 GC (1<50); 1 UNS-BC (<50)	C1	C1	C1	https://doi.org/10.1038/441436-018-0997-7
F248	North America	No	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	-	No disease	-	No	No	No	-
F249	North America	No	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	No	No	No	-
F250	North America	No	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	-	No disease	-	No	No	No	-
F251	North America	No	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	Other	-	No	No	No	-
F252	North America	No	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	-	No	No	C11	-
F253	North America	No	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	No	No	No	-
F254	North America	No	Yes	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 GC; 1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	-
F255	North America	No	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	C3	-
F256	North America	No	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	Other	-	No	No	No	-
F257	North America	No	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	-
F258	North America	No	Yes	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC-only	1 GC (<50)	No	No	No	-
F259	North America	No	Yes	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	2 GC	No	No	No	-
F260	North America	No	Yes	No	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 LBC; 1 GC	C11	C4	C5	-

F261	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F262	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F263	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C9	-
F264	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F265	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	CI2	-
F266	North America	No	Yes	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 GC; 2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C9	-
F267	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F268	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F269	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F270	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F271	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F272	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2023C>T	p.Gln675*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F273	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2038C>T	p.Gln680*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F274	Europe	Yes	No	No	No	c.2056del	p.Glu686Asnfs* 36	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 DGC	No	C13	C4	C1	-
F275	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2080G>T	p.Glu694*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	C5	-
F276	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2101G>T	p.Glu701*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-
F277	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2101G>T	p.Glu701*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	CI4	-
F278	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2124del	p.Ser708Argfs* 14	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F279	Europe	Yes	No	No	Yes	c.2167A>G	p.Met723Val	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD competent	No	Non-truncating	-	Unknown	-	No	No	No	No	-
F280	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2191C>T	p.Arg731*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	-	No disease	-	No	No	No	No	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41436-020-0753-1
F281	North America	No	Yes	No	No	c.2191C>T	p.Arg731*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 DGC (<50)	C4	C4	C2	C1	-
F282	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2191C>T	p.Arg731*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	CI1	-
F283	North America	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	c.2191C>T	p.Arg731*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 GC; 2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F284	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2191C>T	p.Arg731*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-

F285	North America	No	No	Yes	No	c.2191C>T	p.Arg731*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	1 LBC (<55); 2 UNS-BC (<50)	C10	C10	C3	C9	-
F286	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2191C>T	p.Arg731*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F287	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2191C>T	p.Arg731*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-
F288	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2191C>T	p.Arg731*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	-	No	No	C11	-	-
F289	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2191C>T	p.Arg731*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F290	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.2191C>T	p.Arg731*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	GC+BC	2 GC	No	No	No	No	-
F291	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2191C>T	p.Arg731*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	-	No	No	No	C5	-
F292	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2191C>T	p.Arg731*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F293	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2191C>T	p.Arg731*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F294	North America	No	No	Yes	No	c.2191C>T	p.Arg731*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	GC+BC	1 LBC; 2 GC	C11	C11	C3	C11	-
F295	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2191C>T	p.Arg731*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F296	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2191C>T	p.Arg731*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F297	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2191C>T	p.Arg731*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F298	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2298+2dupT	-	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Splice-site/intronic variant	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F299	North America	No	No	Yes	No	c.2298+2dupT	-	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Splice-site/intronic variant	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F300	North America	No	No	Yes	No	c.2298+2dupT	-	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Splice-site/intronic variant	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	1 LBC (<70)	No	C14	C5	No	-
F301	North America	No	No	Yes	No	c.2298+2dupT	-	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Splice-site/intronic variant	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	1 LBC (<50)	C10	C10	C3	C9	-
F302	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.2298+2dupT	-	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Splice-site/intronic variant	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C14	-
F303	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.2298+2dupT	-	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Splice-site/intronic variant	Non-coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	GC+BC	1 GC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-
F304	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.2299-7_230dup	p.Pro768Leu(s)27	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	C3	-
F305	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.2341C>T	p.Gln781*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	BC-only	-	No	No	No	C13	-
F306	Europe	Yes	No	No	No	c.2358C>G	p.Tyr786*	Actin cytoskeleton binding	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familiar	GC+BC	1 LBC (<70); 1 GC	C11	C11	C4	No	-
F307	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.2393-2394:inst	p.Glu799Arg(s)79	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	https://doi.org/10.1038/4436-020-0753-1

F308	Europe	Yes	No	No	No	c.2418_2422dup	p.Val808Glyfs* 13	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC-only	1 DGC (<50)	C4	C4	C4	C2	C1	-
F309	North America	No	Yes	No	No	c.2443_2462dup	p.Ala822Profs* 4	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	-	No	No	No	C3	https://doi.org/10.1038/41436-020-0753-1
F310	North America	No	No	Yes	No	c.2447del	p.Met816Serfs* 3	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 DGC	No	C13	No	C4	C1	-
F311	North America	No	Yes	No	No	c.2458C>T	p.Gln820*	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	No	-
F312	North America	No	Yes	No	No	c.2491C>T	p.Gln831*	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Nonsense	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	No	https://doi.org/10.1038/41436-020-0753-1
F313	Europe	Yes	No	No	No	c.2493G>C	p.Gln831His	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD incompetent	No	Non-truncating	Personal	GC-only	1 DGC (<50)	C4	C4	C2	C1	-	
F314	Europe	Yes	Yes	No	No	c.2493G>C	p.Gln831His	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD incompetent	No	Non-truncating	-	Unknown	-	No	No	No	No	No	-
F315	Europe	Yes	Yes	No	No	c.2493G>C	p.Gln831His	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD incompetent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	4 UNS.BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	C3	-
F316	Europe	Yes	No	No	No	c.2493G>C	p.Gln831His	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD incompetent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 LBC (<50); 1 UNS-BC (<50)	C10	C10	C3	C3	-	
F317	Europe	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	c.2493G>C	p.Gln831His	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD incompetent	No	Non-truncating	Personal	Other	-	No	No	No	No	No	-
F318	Europe	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	c.2493G>C	p.Gln831His	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD incompetent	No	Non-truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	No	-
F319	Europe	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	c.2493G>C	p.Gln831His	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD incompetent	No	Non-truncating	Personal	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	C3	-
F320	Europe	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	c.2493G>C	p.Gln831His	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD incompetent	No	Non-truncating	Familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	No	-
F321	Europe	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	c.2493G>C	p.Gln831His	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD incompetent	No	Non-truncating	Familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	No	-

F322	North America	No	No	Yes	c.2504C>T	p.Ala855Val	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD incompetent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	C12	-	
F323	North America	No	No	Yes	c.2510A>C	p.Tyr837Ser	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD incompetent	No	Non-truncating	Familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-	
F324	North America	No	Yes	No	c.2509_2552dup	p.Leu852Thrfs*25	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 LBC	C10	C10	C3	C11	-	
F325	North America	No	No	Yes	c.2509_2552dup	p.Leu852Thrfs*25	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-	
F326	North America	No	No	Yes	c.2509_2552dup	p.Leu852Thrfs*25	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	-	
F327	Europe	Yes	No	No	c.2558A>G	p.Asn853Ser	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD incompetent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familial	GC-only	1 DGC (<50); 2 GC	C1	C1	C1	C1	-	
F328	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	c.2558A>G	p.Asn853Ser	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD incompetent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-	
F329	Europe	Yes	No	No	c.2617_2620del	p.Glu874Asnfs*18	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	GC+BC	1 LBC; 3 GC	C11	C11	C4	No	-	
F330	North America	No	No	Yes	c.2617_2620dup	p.Lys874Argfs*5	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	C3	-
F331	North America	No	No	Yes	c.2621_2622del	p.Lys874Thrfs*3	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	C3	https://doi.org/10.1038/641436-020-0753-1
F332	North America	No	Yes	Yes	c.2621_2622del	p.Lys874Thrfs*3	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	GC-only	1 GC	No	No	No	No	-	
F333	North America	No	No	Yes	c.2621_2622del	p.Lys874Thrfs*3	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-	
F334	North America	No	No	Yes	c.2621_2622del	p.Lys874Thrfs*3	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	Familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	C14	-
F335	North America	No	No	Yes	c.2621_2624dup	p.Asp876Gluufs*4	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-	

F336	North America	No	No	No	Yes	c.262L_262Zdup	p.Asp876Glufs* 4	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	-	No	No	No	No	No	-
F337	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.2627dup	p.Asp876Glufs* 2	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-	
F338	North America	No	Yes	No	Yes	c.463L_263Zdup	p.Thr878Argfs* 15	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-	
F339	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	c.2633C-G	p.Thr878Arg	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD incompetent	No	Non-truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-	
F340	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.2635_2636del	p.Gln879Aspfs* 4	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	-	No disease	-	No	No	No	No	https://doi.org/10.1038/41436-020-0753-1	
F341	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.2635_2636del	p.Gln879Aspfs* 4	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding truncating	NMD incompetent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	https://doi.org/10.1038/41436-020-0753-1	
F342	Asia	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.2678C-T	p.Pro893Leu	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Missense	Coding non-truncating	NMD incompetent	No	Non-truncating	-	Eye disorders-only	2 FEVR	No	No	No	No	-	doi: 10.1172/OI13989
F343	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.2719dup	p.Ter907Leufs* 15	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding non-truncating	NMD incompetent	No	Non-truncating	-	Unknown	-	No	No	No	No	-	
F344	North America	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	c.2719dup	p.Ter907Leufs* 15	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding non-truncating	NMD incompetent	No	Non-truncating	Familial	GC+BC	1 GC; 2 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-	
F345	North America	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	c.2719dup	p.Ter907Leufs* 15	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding non-truncating	NMD incompetent	No	Non-truncating	Familial	GC+BC	1 GC	No	No	No	No	-	
F346	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	c.2719dup	p.Ter907Leufs* 15	Actin cytoskeleton binding - NMD incompetent	Frameshift	Coding non-truncating	NMD incompetent	No	Non-truncating	Personal	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-	
F347	Europe	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	5'UTR_EX74del	-	Adherens junction binding	Large deletion	Large CNV	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	-	Other diseases	-	No	No	No	No	-	
F348	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	5'UTR_EX17dup	-	All protein junction binding	Large duplication	Large CNV	NMD competent	Unknown	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	-	
F349	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	EX4_7dup	-	Adherens junction binding	Large duplication	Large CNV	NMD competent	Unknown	Truncating	Personal/familial	Other	-	No	No	No	No	-	
F350	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	EX11del	-	M-fragment	Large deletion	Large CNV	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	https://doi.org/10.1038/41436-020-0753-1	
F351	North America	No	No	Yes	Yes	5'UTR_EX18del	-	All protein	Large deletion	Large CNV	NMD competent	Yes	Truncating	Personal/familial	BC-only	1 UNS-BC (<50)	No	No	No	No	https://doi.org/10.1038/41436-020-0753-1	

Supplementary Table 3: Dataset in numbers regarding family history, phenotypical distribution and age of onset of Cohorts-I, -II and -III.

	Cohort-I characteristics		Cohort-II characteristics		Cohort-III characteristics	
	Number (n)	Frequency (%)	Number (n)	Frequency (%)	Number (n)	Frequency (%)
Number of individuals	221	100,00	310	100,00	1050	100,00
Probands	71	32,13	59	19,03	295	28,10
Relatives	150	67,87	251	80,97	755	71,90
Cancer history (per family)						
Familial history of cancer	3	4,23	9	15,25	71	24,07
Personal history of cancer	17	23,94	6	10,17	52	17,63
Personal/familial history of cancer	38	53,52	44	74,58	146	49,49
No personal/familial cancer history	11	15,49	0	0,00	20	6,78
Unknown	2	2,82	0	0,00	6	2,03
Personal/familial cancer history (specific)						
Personal/familial history of GC	14	19,72	15	25,42	10	3,39
Personal/familial history of BC	21	29,58	10	16,95	186	63,05
Personal/familial history of GC+BC	10	14,08	34	57,63	19	6,44
Personal/familial history of OTHER cancer	13	18,31	0	0,00	53	17,97
Personal/familial history of Eye disorders	9	12,68	0	0,00	12	4,07
Personal/familial history of BC+Eye disorders	0	0,00	0	0,00	1	0,34
Personal/familial history of other disorders	1	1,41	0	0,00	1	0,34
No Personal/familial history of disease	1	1,41	0	0,00	7	2,37
Unknown	2	2,82	0	0,00	6	2,03
Probands' phenotypic presentation						
Diffuse/signet ring cells GC (DGC)	19	21,59	14	19,72	2	0,58
GC unknown histotype (GC)	0	0,00	2	2,82	2	0,58
Lobular BC (LBC)	5	5,68	14	19,72	0	0,00
BC unspecified histotype (UNS-BC) (includes ductal)	18	20,45	18	25,35	140	40,94
Colorectal cancer (CRC)	5	5,68	2	2,82	15	4,39
Ovarian cancer (OC)	5	5,68	0	0,00	7	2,05
Prostate cancer (PC)	3	3,41	1	1,41	12	3,51
Lung cancer (LC)	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
Pancreatic cancer (PCC)	0	0,00	1	1,41	4	1,17
Skin cancer (non-Melanoma) (SKC)	0	0,00	1	1,41	8	2,34
Melanoma (MEL)	2	2,27	0	0,00	6	1,75
Eye Disorders (EYED)	9	10,23	0	0,00	13	3,80
Other phenotypes (OTH)	18	20,45	9	12,68	56	16,37
No cancer in carriers (Healthy)	4	4,55	9	12,68	77	22,51
Relatives' phenotypic presentation						
Diffuse/signet ring cells GC (DGC)	24	14,91	5	1,76	0	0,00
GC unknown histotype (GC)	14	8,70	40	14,08	30	3,54
Lobular BC (LBC)	3	1,86	5	1,76	0	0,00
BC unspecified histotype (UNS-BC) (includes ductal)	26	16,15	61	21,48	249	29,40
Colorectal cancer (CRC)	5	3,11	18	6,34	58	6,85
Ovarian cancer (OC)	3	1,86	11	3,87	35	4,13
Prostate cancer (PC)	5	3,11	24	8,45	58	6,85
Lung cancer (LC)	3	1,86	23	8,10	70	8,26
Pancreatic cancer (PCC)	4	2,48	9	3,17	36	4,25
Skin cancer (non-Melanoma) (SKC)	2	1,24	4	1,41	28	3,31
Melanoma (MEL)	4	2,48	6	2,11	21	2,48
Eye Disorders (EYED)	19	11,80	0	0,00	22	2,60
Other phenotypes (OTH)	27	16,77	73	25,70	227	26,80
No cancer in carriers (Healthy)	22	13,66	5	1,76	13	1,53
Age of disease onset	Mean±SD	Age range	Mean±SD	Age range	Mean±SD	Age range
In affected probands	48.86±14.25	23 - 92	51.50±15.96	15 - 83	52.48±14.43	01 - 92
In affected relatives	53.93±17.03	01 - 85	60.47±14.80	20 - 89	59.22±15.00	03 - 96
In affected relatives with known carrier status	45.50±18.75	01 - 79	57.62±10.16	33 - 70	44.93±21.88	04 - 80

Supplementary Table 4: Retrospective analysis in a clinical cancer cohort that underwent pan-cancer multigene panel testing from the United States (n=270 *CTNNA1* truncating variant (TV) carriers; n=414 *CDH1* pathogenic and likely pathogenic (P/LP) carriers; n=37.428 *CTNNA1* and *CDH1* wild-type (WT) individuals as controls).

<i>CTNNA1</i> TV Cohort	N (%)	<i>CDH1</i> LP/P Cohort		MGPT-WT Cohort	
		Sex	N (%)	Sex	N (%)
Female	236 (87.41%)	Female	323 (78.02%)	Female	32275 (86.67%)
Male	33 (12.22%)	Male	79 (19.08%)	Male	5009 (13.45%)
Unknown	1 (0.37%)	Unknown	12 (2.90%)	Unknown	2 (0.01%)
Ethnicity/Race		Ethnicity/Race		Ethnicity/Race	
Black/African American	23 (8.52%)	Black/African American	32 (7.73%)	Black/African American	2740 (7.36%)

Ashkenazi Jewish	21 (7.78%)	Ashkenazi Jewish	12 (2.90%)	Ashkenazi Jewish	1756 (4.71%)
Asian	7 (2.59%)	Asian	10 (2.42%)	Asian	1364 (3.66%)
White	145 (53.70%)	White	266 (64.25%)	White	23625 (63.43%)
Hispanic	12 (4.44%)	Hispanic	29 (7.00%)	Hispanic	2140 (5.75%)
Middle Eastern	0 (0%)	Middle Eastern	7 (1.69%)	Middle Eastern	249 (0.67%)
Mixed Ethnicity	5 (1.85%)	Mixed Ethnicity	10 (2.42%)	Mixed Ethnicity	1338 (3.59%)
Native American	1 (0.37%)	Native American	0 (0%)	Native American	38 (0.10%)
Other/Unknown	55 (20.34%)	Other/Unknown	4 (0.97%)	Other/Unknown	4036 (10.84%)
Gastric Cancer		Gastric Cancer		Gastric Cancer	
Yes	7 (2.59%)	Yes	66 (15.94%)	Yes	159 (0.43%)
No/not reported	264 (97.78%)	No/not reported	348 (84.06%)	No/not reported	37089 (99.57%)
LBC		LBC		LBC	
Yes	10 (3.70%)	Yes	81 (19.57%)	Yes	1210 (3.25%)
No/not reported	261 (96.67%)	No/not reported	333 (80.43%)	No/not reported	36038 (96.75%)

Supplementary Table 5: Distribution and abbreviation of phenotypes in Cohort-I (n=223 phenotypes)

Phenotype	Abbreviation	Number of cases (n)	Cases frequency (%)	Designated group
Unspecified breast cancer	UNS-BC	44	19,73	UNS-BC
Diffuse gastric cancer	DGC	44	19,73	DGC
Macular dystrophy patterned 2	MDPT2	28	12,56	EYE DISORDERS
Unspecified gastric cancer	GC	14	6,28	GC
Colorectal cancer	CRC	10	4,48	CRC
Prostate cancer	PC	8	3,59	PC
Ovarian cancer	OC	8	3,59	OC
Lobular breast cancer	LBC	8	3,59	LBC
Melanoma	MEL	6	2,69	OTHER
Pancreatic cancer	PCC	5	2,24	OTHER
Unknown disease status/Unknown primary	Unknown	6	2,69	OTHER
Lung cancer	LC	3	1,35	OTHER
Brain cancer	BRC	3	1,35	OTHER
Leukemia	LEU	3	1,35	OTHER
Multinodular goiter	MG	3	1,35	OTHER
Skin cancer (non-melanoma)	SKC	2	0,90	OTHER
Kidney cancer	KC	2	0,90	OTHER
Bladder cancer	BDC	2	0,90	OTHER
Urothelial cancer	UrC	2	0,90	OTHER
Polyposis	POLYP	2	0,90	OTHER
Lymphoma	LYMP	2	0,90	OTHER
Uterine cancer	UTC	1	0,45	OTHER
Cervical cancer	CXC	1	0,45	OTHER
Liver cancer	LVC	1	0,45	OTHER
Oesophageal cancer	OEC	1	0,45	OTHER
Head and neck cancer	H&N	1	0,45	OTHER
Testicular cancer	TsC	1	0,45	OTHER
Gynologic cancer	GyC	1	0,45	OTHER
Appendix cancer	AxC	1	0,45	OTHER
Gallbladder cancer	GBC	1	0,45	OTHER
Sarcoma	SARC	1	0,45	OTHER
Adrenal cancer	ACC	1	0,45	OTHER
Endometrial cancer	EC	1	0,45	OTHER
Neuroendocrine tumor	NT	1	0,45	OTHER
Cleft lip/palate	CLP	1	0,45	OTHER
Epileptic encephalopathy	EPE	1	0,45	OTHER
Hypodontia	HYP	1	0,45	OTHER
Microdontia	MIC	1	0,45	OTHER
Peritoneal carcinosis	PEC	1	0,45	OTHER

Supplementary Table 6: Detailed description of individuals with small intramucosal signet ring cell carcinomas (SRCC; pT1a lesions) found in this study (Cohorts-I to -IV), who are relatives of DGC probands.

Case no.	Family no.	Cohort	Case	Confirmed carrier?	Phenotype	Age	No. of lesions	First finding through:	Family details
1	F005	I	Probands' 1st degree relative	YES	SRCC	75	1	Surveillance (gastric biopsy)	Family F005 encloses 7 advanced DGC cases; the <i>CTNNA1</i> variant found in F005 is present in another 3 families, 2 of which meeting full HDGC criteria
2	F005	I	Probands' 1st degree relative	YES	SRCC	41	Multiple	Surveillance (gastric biopsy)	
3	F005	I	Probands' 2nd degree relative	YES	SRCC	47	Multiple	Surveillance (gastric biopsy)	
4	F005	I	Probands' 2nd degree relative	YES	SRCC	41	Multiple	Surveillance (gastric biopsy)	
5	F005	I	Probands' relative	YES	SRCC	79	1	Surveillance (gastric biopsy)	
6	F005	I	Probands' relative	YES	SRCC	51	1	Surveillance (gastric biopsy)	
7	F166	I	Probands' 1st degree relative	YES	SRCC	37	3	Surveillance (gastric biopsy)	Family F166 has one case of advanced DGC before age 50 (proband)
8	F247	I	Probands' 2nd degree relative	YES	SRCC	32	3	Risk reduction (Prophylactic gastrectomy)	Family F247 has 3 cases of advanced DGC + 2 GC cases with unconfirmed histology; The variant found in family F247 is present in another 25 families, 1 of which meeting full HDGC criteria
9	F247	I	Probands' 2nd degree relative	YES	SRCC	20	1	Risk reduction (Prophylactic gastrectomy)	

Supplementary Table 7: Upstream activating sequences (UAS) lines used in this study to establish the *CTNNA1* humanized *Drosophila melanogaster* *in vivo* model.

Name	Insert	Chromosome	Vector backbone	Insertion method	Selection gene
pPW-CTNNA1 WT	Human WT CTNNA1 cDNA	3	pPW-attB	P-element	<i>White</i>
pPW-aCAT208	Human CTNNA1 cDNA containing the c.208G>A missense variant	3	pPW-attB	P-element	<i>White</i>
pPW-aCAT2023	Human CTNNA1 cDNA containing the c.2023C>T nonsense variant	3	pPW-attB	P-element	<i>White</i>

Supplementary Table 8: Univariate logistic regression analysis on Cohort-I (performed to attain the phenotypes to be analysed in the Firth's Bias-Reduced Logistic Regression from Fig.3b).

Variables	Total ^a		Molecular Effect prediction				P-value
	(n=223)		Truncating (n=112)		Non-Truncating (n=111)		
	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Mean age (SD), years							
Sex (female) ^b	138	62.2	65	58.6	73	65.8	0.268
Phenotypes							
DGC	43	19.3	39	34.8	4	3.6	<0.001
GC	14	6.3	12	10.7	2	1.8	0.006
LBC	8	3.6	7	6.3	1	0.9	0.032
UNS-BC	44	19.7	10	8.9	34	30.6	<0.001
CRC	10	4.5	5	4.5	5	4.5	0.988
OC	8	3.6	2	1.8	6	5.4	0.146
PC	8	3.6	3	2.7	5	4.5	0.464
Eye disorder	28	12.6	0	0.0	28	25.2	<0.001
Other	60	26.9	34	30.4	26	23.4	0.243

^aHealthy cases were removed from this table; ^b1 cases missing sex data;

Supplementary Table 9: Analysis B: Pick-up rate of *CTNNA1*-truncating carrier families with classic* and newly proposed *CTNNA1* expanded criteria (n=81 families; Cohorts-I & -II)

HDGC criteria		Description	Families with criteria	Pick-up rate
Blair et al. 2020*	C1	≥2 cases of GC in family regardless of age, with at least one DGC	13	16.0%
	C2	≥1 case of DGC at any age, and ≥1 case of LBC <70 years of age	2	2.5%
	C3	≥2 cases of LBC in family members <50 years of age	1	1.2%
	C4	DGC <50 years of age	13	16.0%
Pelaez et al. 2023*	C10	≥2 cases of BC, 1 confirmed LBC	7	8.6%
	C11	History of GC and BC, 1 confirmed LBC regardless of age	7	8.6%
	C12	Isolated LBC in individuals with <55 years of age	2	2.5%
CTNNA1 expanded criteria	C13	History of GC and BC, one confirmed DGC regardless of age	5	6.2%
	C14	Isolated LBC in individuals aged <70 years of age	2	2.5%
No criteria		8/29 with GC-only	No. families	Non-HDGC families (%)
		3/29 with BC-only		
		15/29 with GC+BC		
		3/29 with other cancers		
			29	35.8%

Supplementary Figure 10: Detailed description of the different set of HDGC clinical criteria used to evaluate the criteria performance in Fig.4a.

Classic criteria		Classic + CTNNA1 expanded criteria		Yale criteria		Porto criteria				
Blair et al. 2020	1	≥2 cases of GC in family regardless of age, with at least one DGC, regardless of age	1	≥2 cases of GC in family regardless of age, with at least one DGC, regardless of age	Lerner et al. 2023	1	DGC at any age in proband or FDR	Present study	1	≥2 cases of GC in family regardless of age, with at least one DGC, regardless of age
	2	≥1 case of DGC at any age, and ≥1 case of LBC <70 years of age	2	≥1 case of DGC at any age, and ≥1 case of LBC <70 years of age		2	≥2 cases GC in FDR or SDR, ≥1 diagnosed at age ≤50		2	DGC <50 years of age
	3	≥2 cases of LBC in family members <50 years of age	3	≥2 cases of LBC in family members <50 years of age	NCCN guidelines 2024	3	BC at age ≤50	3	≥2 cases of BC, at least 1 confirmed LBC	
	4	DGC <50 years of age	4	DGC <50 years of age		4	Triple-negative BC	4	Familial/personal history of GC and BC, one confirmed DGC or LBC, regardless of age	
	5	DGC at any age in individuals of Māori ethnicity	5	DGC at any age in individuals of Māori ethnicity		5	Multiple primary BC (in same individual)	5	Isolated LBC in individuals aged <70 years of age	
	6	DGC at any age in individuals with personal/family history (1 st degree) of cleft lip/palate	6	DGC at any age in individuals with personal/family history (1 st degree) of cleft lip/palate		6	LBC with personal or family history of DGC			
	7	History of DGC and LBC, both diagnosed <70 years of age	7	History of DGC and LBC, both diagnosed <70 years of age		7	Male BC			
	8	Bilateral LBC, diagnosed <70 years of age	8	Bilateral LBC, diagnosed <70 years of age		8	BC + Ashkenazi Jewish ancestry			
	9	Gastric in situ SRC or pagetoid spread of SRC <50 years of age	9	Gastric in situ SRC or pagetoid spread of SRC <50 years of age		9	BC + close relative* with BC at age ≤ 50			
Garcia-Pelaez et al. 2023	10	≥2 cases of BC, at least 1 confirmed LBC	10	≥2 cases of BC, at least 1 confirmed LBC	10	BC + close relative* with male BC				
	11	History of GC and BC, 1 confirmed LBC regardless of age	11	History of GC and BC, 1 confirmed LBC regardless of age	11	BC + close relative* with ovarian cancer				
	12	Isolated LBC in individuals with <55 years of age	12	Isolated LBC in individuals with <55 years of age	12	BC + close relative* with pancreatic cancer				
			CTNNA1 expanded criteria - Present Study	13	History of GC and BC, one confirmed DGC regardless of age	13	BC + close relative* with metastatic (or high- or very high group) prostate cancer			
			14	Isolated LBC in individuals aged <70 years of age	14	≥3 diagnoses of breast and/or prostate cancer (any grade) on the same side of the family				

Supplementary Table 11: Confusion matrixes of the performance analysis on th different sets of HDGC criteria.

Porto criteria	Meets criteria	Does not meet criteria
Truncating variant	52	234
Non-truncating variant	5	60
Classic criteria	Meets criteria	Does not meet criteria
Truncating variant	45	241
Non-truncating variant	4	61
Classic + CTNNA1 expanded criteria	Meets criteria	Does not meet criteria
Truncating variant	52	234
Non-truncating variant	5	60
Yale criteria	Meets criteria	Does not meet criteria
Truncating variant	150	136
Non-truncating variant	23	42
NO criteria	Meets criteria	Does not meet criteria
Truncating variant	130	156
Non-truncating variant	42	23

Supplementary Table 12: Distribution and abbreviation of phenotypes in Analysis-D (n=1099 disease phenotypes).

Phenotype	Abbreviation	Number of cases (n)	Cases frequency (%)	Designated group
Unspecified breast cancer	UNS-BC	389	35,40	UNS-BC
Colorectal cancer	CRC	73	6,64	CRC
Prostate cancer	PC	70	6,37	PC
Lung cancer	LC	70	6,37	LC
Unknown disease status/Unknown primary	Unknown	65	5,91	OTHER
Ovarian cancer	OC	42	3,82	OC
Pancreatic cancer	PCC	40	3,64	PCC
Skin cancer (non-melanoma)	SKC	35	3,18	SKC
Unspecified gastric cancer	GC	32	2,91	GC
Macular dystrophy patterned 2	MDPT2	28	2,55	EYE DISORDERS
Melanoma	MEL	27	2,46	MEL
Brain cancer	BRC	21	1,91	OTHER
Leukemia	LEU	20	1,82	OTHER
Kidney cancer	KC	16	1,46	OTHER
Thyroid Cancer	ThC	16	1,46	OTHER
Lymphoma	LYMP	15	1,36	OTHER
Cervical cancer	CXC	13	1,18	OTHER
Bone cancer	BNC	11	1,00	OTHER
Liver cancer	LVC	11	1,00	OTHER
Uterine cancer	UtC	10	0,91	OTHER
Bladder cancer	BDC	10	0,91	OTHER
Multiple Myeloma	MMYE	8	0,73	OTHER
Throat Cancer	TrC	8	0,73	OTHER
Familial Exudative Vitreoretinopathy	FEVR	6	0,55	EYE DISORDERS
Oesophageal cancer	OEC	6	0,55	OTHER
Testicular cancer	TsC	5	0,45	OTHER
Gynologic cancer	GyC	4	0,36	OTHER
Appendix cancer	AxC	4	0,36	OTHER
Gallbladder cancer	GBC	4	0,36	OTHER
Head and neck cancer	H&N	3	0,27	OTHER
Multinodular goiter	MG	3	0,27	OTHER
Polyposis	POLYP	3	0,27	OTHER
Sarcoma	SARC	3	0,27	OTHER
Abdominal cancer	AC	2	0,18	OTHER
Adrenal cancer	ACC	2	0,18	OTHER
Diffuse gastric cancer	DGC	2	0,18	DGC

Eye Cancer	EYC	2	0,18	OTHER
Vulvar Cancer	VC	2	0,18	OTHER
Anal Cancer	ANC	1	0,09	OTHER
Cleft lip/palate	CLP	1	0,09	OTHER
Endometrial cancer	EC	1	0,09	OTHER
Epileptic encephalopathy	EPE	1	0,09	OTHER
Gastrointestinal stromal tumor	GIST	1	0,09	OTHER
Hypodontia	HYP	1	0,09	OTHER
Kaposi sarcoma	KS	1	0,09	OTHER
Myelodysplastic syndromes (MDS)	MDS	1	0,09	OTHER
Mucoepidermoid carcinoma	MEC	1	0,09	OTHER
Microdontia	MIC	1	0,09	OTHER
Neuroendocrine tumor	NT	1	0,09	OTHER
Peritoneal carcinosis	PEC	1	0,09	OTHER
Primary peritoneal serous carcinoma	PPSC	1	0,09	OTHER
Urothelial cancer	UrC	1	0,09	OTHER
vitelliform macular degeneration	VMD	1	0,09	EYE DISORDERS
Gastrointestinal carcinoma	GIC	1	0,09	OTHER
Laryngeal cancer	LRYC	1	0,09	OTHER
Oral Cancer	OrC	1	0,09	OTHER

Supplementary Table 13: Univariate logistic regression analysis and subsequently Firth's Bias-Reduced Logistic Regression model only on the individuals with confirmed carrier status in Analysis-D (n=299 disease phenotypes).

Firth's Bias-Reduced Logistic Regression Only carriers Sub-cohort					
Phenotypes	Coefficients	Odds ratio	Lower bound	Upper bound	P-value
UNS-BC	-0.53	0.59	0.32	1.08	0.0867
EYE DISORDERS	3.30	27.03	9.32	105.62	<0.0001

	Molecular Effect prediction						P-value
	Total		CTNNA1 truncating variants		CTNNA1 non-truncating variants		
	(n=299)		(n=217)		(n=82)		
	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Mean age (SD), years ^a	52.0	(15.0)	53.1	(14.7)	48.3	(15.7)	0.031
Sex (female) ^b	232	77.9	176	81.5	56	68.3	0.014
Phenotypes							
DGC	2	0.7	0	0	2	2.4	0.075*
GC	3	1.0	3	1.4	0	0	0.564*
LBC	0	0	0	0	0	0	-
UNS-BC	146	48.8	123	56.7	23	28.0	<0.001
CRC	16	5.4	10	4.6	6	7.3	0.390*
OC	7	2.3	3	1.4	4	4.9	0.093*
PC	12	4.0	10	4.6	2	2.4	0.522*
LC	0	0	0	0	0	0	-
PCC	4	1.3	4	1.8	0	0	0.578*
SKC	8	2.7	7	3.2	1	1.2	0.453*
MEL	9	3.0	7	3.2	2	2.4	1.000*
EYE DISORDERS	33	11.0	3	1.4	30	36.6	<0.001
Other	59	19.7	47	21.7	12	14.6	0.173

^a 52 cases with missing age of diagnosis (excluding healthy)

^b 1 case with missing sex data (excluding healthy)

* Fischer's exact test

Supplementary Table 14: List of variants reported that were excluded from the study per high variant MAF in GnomAS v4.0.0 and/or were considered variants of low impact.

Variants excluded	No. Families	Motif for exclusion	Vairant type	Max freq in GnomAD v4.0.0
c.536C>T	2	High frequency	Missense	0.002023
c.618G>C	1	High frequency	Missense	0.01839
c.770A>G	1	High frequency	Missense	0.003914
c.1047G>A	1	High frequency/variant type	Synonymous	0.003165
c.2154G>A	1	High frequency/variant type	Synonymous	0.00288
c.-7T>C	5	Variant type	5'UTR	0.0001308
c.105+20A>C	1	Variant type	Intronic (± 4 bp)	0.0001922
c.333C>T	1	Variant type	Synonymous	0.00005782
c.859-19G>A	1	Variant type	Intronic (± 4 bp)	0.00007238
c.867C>T	2	Variant type	Synonymous	0.00009648
c.1144-5A>G	7	Variant type	Intronic (± 4 bp)	0.0001029
c.1149C>T	1	Variant type	Synonymous	0.0000147
c.1185G>A	1	Variant type	Synonymous	0.0001653
c.1389+11A>G	1	Variant type	Intronic (± 4 bp)	0.000008837
c.1390-20A>G	1	Variant type	Intronic (± 4 bp)	-
c.1422A>G	1	Variant type	Synonymous	-
c.1506C>T	1	Variant type	Synonymous	0.00004409
c.1547-9G>A	1	Variant type	Intronic (± 4 bp)	0.0004348
c.1590C>T	1	Variant type	Synonymous	-
c.1743C>T	1	Variant type	Synonymous	0.00007771
c.1747+7G>A	2	Variant type	Intronic (± 4 bp)	-
c.1747+19T>C	1	Variant type	Intronic (± 4 bp)	0.0003087
c.1857T>C	1	Variant type	Synonymous	-
c.2136C>T	2	Variant type	Synonymous	-
c.2274G>A	2	Variant type	Synonymous	0.000008792
c.2434-5C>T	1	Variant type	Intronic (± 4 bp)	0.0005442

Supplementary Table 15: Splicing prediction of *CTNNA1* splice-site variants in Cohorts-I, -II and -III.

VARIANT	Type	Variant final classification	SPLICE AI	NETGENE2	MAXENTSCAN	COMMENTS ON THE SPLICING RESULT
c.105+1G>C	SPLICE-SITE	Truncating	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	INVITAE: Studies have shown that disruption of this splice site results in skipping of exon 2 or exons 2-3, and is expected to result in the loss of the initiator methionine (Invitae). There is another Methionine in the beginning of exon 4 (RESULTS IN TRUNCATION BY START LOSS)
c.106-2A>C	SPLICE-SITE	Truncating	Splicing affected	Unknown	Splicing affected	According to Splice AI, a new acceptor is formed 28bp after the variant. This means that the first 26bp of exon 3 would be recognized as intronic sequence (RESULTS IN TRUNCATION)
c.301+1delG	SPLICE-SITE	Truncating	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	According to Splice AI and NeteGene2, a new splice donor is found 1 bp before de variant. This means that the last bp (G) of exon 3 is recognized as part of the intron (RESULTS IN TRUNCATION)
c.301+1G>A	SPLICE-SITE	Truncating	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	According to Splice AI and NeteGene2, no other donor splice site is recognized. As so, it is predicted that the splicing machinery will only recognize the donor of exon 2, and consequently recognize the whole exon 3 as na intron. This results in skipping of exon 3 (RESULTS IN TRUNCATION)

c.468+1G>A	SPLICE-SITE	Truncating	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	According to Splice AI and NeteGene2, no other donor splice site is recognized. As so, it is predicted that the splicing machinery will only recognize the donor of exon 3, and consequently recognize the whole exon 4 as aN intron. This results in skipping of exon 4 (RESULTS IN TRUNCATION)
c.468+1G>C	SPLICE-SITE	Truncating	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	According to Splice AI and NeteGene2, no other donor splice site is recognized. As so, it is predicted that the splicing machinery will only recognize the donor of exon 3, and consequently recognize the whole exon 4 as aN intron. This results in skipping of exon 4 (RESULTS IN TRUNCATION)
c.588+2T>A	SPLICE-SITE	Non-truncating	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	According to Splice AI and NeteGene2, no other donor splice site is recognized. As so, it is predicted that the splicing machinery will only recognize the donor of exon 4, and consequently recognize the whole exon 5 as an intron. This results in skipping of exon 5 (RESULTS IN AN INFRAME DELETION)
c.1063-1G>A	SPLICE-SITE	Truncating	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	According to Splice AI and NeteGene2, a new splice acceptor is found 1 bp after the variant. This means that the first bp (G) of exon 8 is recognized as part of the intron (RESULTS IN TRUNCATION)
c.1390-2A>C	SPLICE-SITE	Truncating	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	According to Splice AI and NeteGene2, no other acceptor splice site is recognized. As so, it is predicted that the splicing machinery will only recognize the acceptor of exon 12, and consequently recognize the whole exon 11 as an intron. This results in skipping of exon 11 (RESULTS IN TRUNCATION)
c.1390-2A>G	SPLICE-SITE	Truncating	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	According to Splice AI and NeteGene2, no other acceptor splice site is recognized. As so, it is predicted that the splicing machinery will only recognize the acceptor of exon 12, and consequently recognize the whole exon 11 as an intron. This results in skipping of exon 11 (RESULTS IN TRUNCATION)
c.1899+1G>C	SPLICE-SITE	Truncating	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	According to Splice AI and NeteGene2, no other donor splice site is recognized. As so, it is predicted that the splicing machinery will only recognize the donor of exon 12, and consequently recognize the whole exon 13 as an intron. This results in skipping of exon 13 (RESULTS IN TRUNCATION)
c.2010+2_2010+3insC	INTRONIC	Non-truncating	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	Splicing affected	According to Splice AI and NeteGene2, no other donor splice site is recognized. As so, it is predicted that the splicing machinery will only recognize the donor of exon 13, and consequently recognize the whole exon 14 as an intron. This results in skipping of exon 14 (RESULTS IN AN INFRAME DELETION)
c.2298+2dupT	INTRONIC	Truncating	Splicing affected	Unknown	Splicing affected	According to Splice AI and NeteGene2, a second donor splice site that is very strong is still recognized with this variant. The new donor splice site is in the 20 bp of intron 16. This means that the first 20 bp of intron 16 will be recognized as part of exon 16 (RESULTS IN TRUNCATION)

Supplementary methods

Development of a large clinical database comprising CTNNA1 variant carrier families worldwide:

1. Data collection of CTNNA1 variant carrier families

Clinical and molecular data on 405 families carrying rare *CTNNA1* germline variants was collected from October 1st, 2020 until March 31st, 2024. Data was either retrieved from the literature (Majewski et al. 2013; Hansford et al. 2015; Saksens et al. 2016; Shirts et al. 2016; Slavin et al. 2017; Weren et al. 2018; Benusiglio et al. 2019; Clark et al. 2020; de Breuk at al. 2021; Lobo et al. 2021; Tanner et al. 2021) or provided by collaborators from 26 research institutions/diagnostic laboratories and one genetic testing company (Supplementary Tables 1-3). The following parameters were considered for exclusion: *CTNNA1* variants with a maximum allele frequency (MAF) >0.1% in the general population/sub-populations in GnomADv4.0.0 (n=6 families); families carrying a synonymous or intronic variant at position ± 4 bp and not expected to disrupt the canonical splice-site (n=35 families) (Fig.1a; Supplementary Table 14); families reported to have other pathogenic or likely pathogenic variant in other tumour risk syndrome genes (n=13 families). Ultimately, 351 families carrying 179 rare *CTNNA1* germline variants (Fig.1a) were collected and proceeded for analysis. Relatives were included in the study with or without genetic testing confirmation. Only 1st and 2nd degree relatives were included. If a 3rd or higher degree relative was a confirmed variant carrier, they were also included in the study.

Cohort-I entailed 71 European families carrying 54 different *CTNNA1* variants, with 71 carrier probands and 150 relatives, from which 70 had confirmed carrier status. This cohort presented 39 different disease phenotypes occurring 223 times in 221 individuals. The frequency of the HDGC-associated phenotype LBC (the rarest HDGC-associated phenotype in *CTNNA1* carrier families) was used as the lower cut-off to select phenotypes for genotype-phenotype analysis; all phenotypes with a frequency lower than that of LBC in the cohort were clustered together and allocated to category "OTHER" (Fig.1b; Supplementary Table 5). Cohort-I enclosed any family carrying a rare *CTNNA1* germline variant, either coding or affecting a canonical splice-site. Although several families were proposed for genetic diagnosis due to HDGC suspicion, all reported disease phenotypes were included. This cohort englobes the first set of analysis (Analysis-A), in which *CTNNA1*-associated disease spectrum and genotype-phenotype associations were analysed.

Cohort-II included 59 families, specifically non-European, carrying 37 different rare *CTNNA1* germline variants, with 59 carrier probands and 250 relatives, from which 14 had confirmed carrier status. This cohort presented 38 different disease phenotypes occurring 340 times in 309 individuals. Families in Cohort-II were ascertained based on the suspicion of HDGC due to personal and/or family history of DGC, GC and/or LBC. This cohort englobes the second set of analysis (Analysis-B) and was used to propose additional criteria to improve the already established HDGC criteria for *CTNNA1* genetic testing (Blair et al. 2020).

Cohort-III englobes only families not meeting HDGC criteria. 221 *CTNNA1* germline variant carrier families not meeting HDGC criteria. 221 carrier probands and 556 relatives (21 with confirmed carrier status), with a total of 798 disease phenotypes (Fig.1a). Cohort-III, together with families from Cohort-I (n=46 families) and Cohort-II (n=28 families) not meeting HDGC clinical criteria, either 'Classic' (Blair et al. 2020; Garcia-Pelaez et al. 2023) or newly proposed in the present study ('Porto' criteria), comprised the set of clinical data used to performed Analysis-D, aimed to uncover genotype-phenotype associations beyond HDGC (Fig.5a; Supplementary Tables 12 and 13). All phenotypes with a frequency lower than 2% in Cohort-III were clustered together and allocated to category "OTHER" (Fig.5a). 295 carrier probands and 755 relatives, from which 44 had confirmed carrier status, comprised a total of 1099 disease phenotypes and 90 healthy confirmed carriers (Fig.1a).

Cohort-IV comprises a retrospective analysis conducted in accordance with the recommendations of the Western Institutional Review Board (Puyallup, Washington). This cohort englobe 298 individuals with a premature termination germline variant in *CTNNA1* (PTVs) and 414 individuals with a pathogenic or likely pathogenic germline variant in *CDH1* (Supplementary Table 4). Individuals with a likely pathogenic or pathogenic variant in another gene associated with autosomal dominant (AD) cancer predisposition were excluded from this analysis (28 *CTNNA1*-variant carriers). PTVs included nonsense, frameshift, or canonical splice variants predicted to cause aberrant splicing resulting in premature termination. Variants in *CDH1* were classified as pathogenic/likely pathogenic based on ACMG guidelines and ClinGen *CDH1* specifications (Richards et al. 2015; Lee et al. 2018). *CTNNA1* and *CDH1* variant carrier individuals were identified via colon and gastric susceptibility panels, panels targeted to other cancer susceptibility such as breast cancer and pan-cancer susceptibility panels (up to 91 genes). Individuals included in the wildtype (WT) control group (37.428 individuals) had undergone pan-cancer MGPT and had no pathogenic or likely pathogenic variants detected in any gene.

2. Sample acquisition, ethics and patient consent

All patients signed an informed consent to perform the germline testing, which either mentioned a future research related to their susceptibility syndrome or allowing the biobanking of samples for future research. In most institutions, ethics approval was obtained, as this is a retrospective study; in the remaining, local ethics approval was granted. The whole project received appraisal N22/CECRI/2022 from the Committee for Ethical and Responsible Conduct of Research of the study's leading institution, Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde, University of Porto, Portugal.

3. Clinical and variant data curation

Family history for all *CTNNA1* germline variant carrier families integrating this project was revised and compliance with the 2020 (Blair et al. 2020) or 2023 extended criteria (Garcia-Pelaez et al. 2023) for HDGC was analysed ('Classic' criteria). Phenotypes were collected from all individuals (some present more than one phenotype). Age of disease onset for all phenotypes and gastric

and breast cancer histology was collected, when available. Diffuse gastric cancer (DGC), lobular breast cancer (LBC), and gastric cancer (GC) were considered HDGC-related phenotypes. Intramucosal signet ring cell carcinomas (pT1a lesions) found in direct blood relatives with confirmed carrier status from families meeting the classical HDGC criteria (Blair et al. 2020) were considered DGC (n=9) (Supplementary Table 6). All non-LBC breast cancer cases were defined as unspecified breast cancer (UNS-BC). All non-cancer eye related phenotypes were aggregated as eye disorders.

Regarding whole family analysis, “gastric cancer only” refers to families with a GC enrichment, not presenting any BC related phenotype, and including other types of cancer besides GC; “breast cancer only” refers to families with a BC enrichment, either LBC or UNS-BC, not presenting any GC related phenotype, and including other types of cancer besides BC; “gastric cancer and breast cancer” relates to families enriched in both GC and BC related phenotypes; “other cancers” regards families presenting a cancer spectrum completely excluding both GC or BC related phenotypes; “eye disorders” refers to families enriched in eye disorders phenotypes, and may include other cancer phenotypes, except GC or BC.

Regarding variant analysis, nomenclature was standardized according to the Human Genome Variation Society (HGVS) guidelines (den Dunnen et al. 2016) and variants were molecularly clustered as: truncating NMD competent (nonsense, frameshift, start loss, large deletion, large duplication, and canonical splice-site variants in the vicinity of out-of-frame exons causing a premature termination codon before *CTNNA1* last exon); truncating NMD incompetent (nonsense, frameshift, start loss, large deletion, large duplication, and canonical splice-site variants in the vicinity of out-of-frame exons causing a premature termination codon after *CTNNA1* last exon); and non-truncating (missense, in-frame indels and canonical splice-site variants in the vicinity of in-frame exons, regardless of the location in *CTNNA1*). This was classified according to Ensembl Variant Effect Predictor (VEP) (McLaren et al. 2016). All canonical splice-site variants were analysed using NetGene2 version 2.4 (Brunak et al. 1991; Hebsgaard et al. 1996), SpliceAI (Jaganathan et al. 2019) and MaxEntScan (Yeo and Burge 2004) splice-site prediction tools to calculate the impact of each variant on splicing and further classify each splice-site variant as truncating or non-truncating (Supplementary Table 15). Recurrence was considered if the same variant occurred in three or more families.

Establishment of in vitro functional model:

1. Cell culture

Human GC cell line MKN74 (RRID:CVCL_2791) was characterized at IPATIMUP. HEK293T (RRID:CVCL_0063) cell line was purchased from American Type Culture Collection (ATCC). MKN74 cell line was cultured in Roswell Park Memorial Institute 1640 medium (RPMI 1640) (Gibco, Billings, MT, USA), while HEK293T cell line was cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) (Gibco, Billings, MT, USA). Both media were supplemented with 10% foetal bovine serum (FBS) (Biowest, Nuaille, France) and 1% penicillin-streptomycin (10,000 U/mL)

(Gibco, Billings, MT, USA). Cells were maintained under 5% CO₂ humidified atmosphere, at 37°C and confirmed to be mycoplasma free.

2. MKN74 CRISPR-Cas9 genetic editing

To obtain a *CTNNA1* knockout cell line, we CRISPR-Cas9 genetic edited MKN74 cell line. We used Sanger Institute Genome Editing (WGE) (<https://wge.stemcell.sanger.ac.uk/>) and Benchling (<https://benchling.com/>) tools to design single guide RNA (sgRNA) targeting *CTNNA1* introns' 10 and 11. sgRNAs were selected accounting for the highest on-target and lowest off-target scores and ordered as single stranded oligo sequences with *BsmBI-V2* sticky ends for cloning from Alfacell (Carcavelos, Portugal).

Two sgRNAs were paired to be transfected together and cause the deletion of the *CTNNA1* out-of-frame exon 11. Each sgRNA was cloned in LentiCRISPRv2 plasmids, either the GFP-expressing (Addgene plasmid # 52961; <http://n2t.net/addgene:52961>; RRID: Addgene_52961) or the mCherry-expressing (Addgene plasmid #99154; <http://n2t.net/addgene:99154>; RRID: Addgene_99154) version. Briefly, sgRNAs were annealed and plasmids digested using *BsmBI-V2* enzyme from New England Biolabs (Ipswich, MA, USA). Afterwards, a ligation reaction was performed using T4 DNA Ligase from Invitrogen (Carlsbad, CA, USA). Ligation was then transformed into One Shot™ Stbl3™ Chemically Competent *Escherichia coli* from ThermoFisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA, Catalog number: C737303) by heat shock. Positive colonies were PCR selected. Briefly, colonies' DNA was extracted using plasmid miniprep kit from NZYTech (Lisbon, Portugal) and Multiplex PCR kit from Qiagen (Venlo, Netherlands) was used to amplify the insert region (primers in Table S6). Verified positive colonies were then massively expanded to extract high-quality plasmid DNA using plasmid maxi kit from Qiagen (Venlo, Netherlands), according to manufacturer's protocol. High-quality plasmids were transfected in HEK293T cells using Lipofectamine3000 from Invitrogen (Carlsbad, CA, USA) for lentiviral production. pMD2.G (Addgene plasmid #12259; <http://n2t.net/addgene:12259>; RRID: Addgene_12259), and pCMV dr8.91 (Addgene plasmid #8455; <http://n2t.net/addgene:8455>; RRID: Addgene_8455) were used to encapsulate the lentiviruses. Afterwards, MKN74 cells were infected with the lentivirus particles using polybrene infection reagent from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany) at a 1:1 ratio. Fresh medium was added after 48h and cells were incubated for 1 week prior to single cell sorting selection. Herein, cells were sorted for GFP+ and mCherry+ expression using FACS ArialI (BD Biosciences, NJ, USA). Single cell sorted clones were allowed to grow for approximately 3-4 weeks and, afterward, genomic DNA was extracted for genotyping using the tissue gDNA Isolation kit from NZYTech (Lisbon, Portugal), according to manufacturer's protocol. Genotyping was performed by PCR using primers surrounding the deletion sequence and, afterwards, PCR products were sanger sequenced using BigDye™ Terminator v3.1 Cycle Sequencing Kit (Applied Biosystems, Waltham, MA, USA) and analysed using Applied Biosystems 3130xl Genetic Analyzer or Applied Biosystems 3500 Genetic Analyzer (Applied Biosystems, Waltham, MA, USA).

3. MKN74 CTNNA1 Ex11Del isogenic cell line characterization

To characterize MKN74 *CTNNA1* Ex11Del at the RNA level, total RNA was isolated using the mirVana™ miRNA Isolation Kit (# AM1561; Invitrogen™, Carlsbad, CA, USA). Briefly, medium was removed, and cells were washed twice with cold 1x PBS. Then, cells were lysed and incubated with a miRNA Homogenate Additive for 10 minutes. Afterwards, acidic phenol was added, and samples were centrifuged to separate the organic cellular components. The aqueous supernatant phase containing the RNA was carefully removed and mixed with 1.25 volumes of absolute Ethanol to precipitate RNA. After, samples were transferred to a filter cartridge membrane to retain RNA and subsequently washed multiple times. RNA was ultimately eluted in sterile DNase and RNase free water preheated at 95°C. RNA concentration and quality was measured using NanoDrop® One UV-Vis Spectrophotometer from ThermoFisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA).

High quality RNA was then used to synthesize complementary DNA (cDNA). For that, SuperScript® II reverse transcriptase from ThermoFisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA) was used to convert 1µg of template RNA, according to the manufacturers' protocol. Briefly, random primers were added to RNA and incubated at 70°C for 10 min. After, a mix containing 0.75µL of SuperScript® II reverse transcriptase, 4µL of SuperScript® II buffer, 2µL of 0.1M dithiothreitol (DTT), 1µL of 10mM deoxynucleotide solution (dNTPs), 0.2µL of RNAsin (40 U/µL) and 0.75µL of sterile water was added to RNA and was incubated at 37°C for 1 hour.

CTNNA1 RNA expression was analysed by reverse transcriptase qPCR (RT-qPCR). For that, two *CTNNA1* probes were used: binding exons 3-4 (Hs.PT.58.14970051) or exons 13-14 (Hs.PT.58.787439). 18s probe (custom assay) was used as an endogenous control. All probes were purchased from Integrated DNA Technologies (Coralville, IA, USA). Results were analysed using ABI Prism 7500 Sequence Detection System (Applied Biosystems, Waltham, MA, USA). *CTNNA1* relative expression was calculated using the comparative $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_T}$ method ($RQ = 2^{-\Delta\Delta C_T}$, where $\Delta\Delta C_T = \Delta C_{T\text{Sample}} - \Delta C_{T\text{Control}}$ sample and $\Delta C_T = C_{T\text{CTNNA1}} - C_{T\text{housekeeping gene}}$). MKN74 *CTNNA1* wild-type cells were used as control. For each sample, at least 3 independent replicates were performed.

α E-catenin protein expression and localization were assessed through flow cytometry and immunocytochemistry. For the flow cytometry protocol, cells were detached, washed and fixated in 2% Paraformaldehyde (PFA) (v/v) (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) in 1x PBS. Then, cells were incubated in 0.7% Tween-20 (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) in 1x PBS to destabilize the cell membrane and incubated with a blocking solution with 3% Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) (v/w) (NZYTech, Lisbon, Portugal) in 1x PBS. Afterwards, cells were incubated with a primary antibody: mouse anti alpha Catenin Monoclonal Antibody alpha-CAT-7A4 (Catalog # 13-9700) or rabbit anti Catenin alpha-1 Monoclonal Antibody (J.783.6) (Catalog # MA5-14986) (1:200 dilution, 60 minutes incubation at 4°C, from ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). The first has affinity to the C-terminal α -catenin region, while the former has affinity to the N-terminal α -catenin region. The secondary antibodies used were: Goat anti-Mouse IgG (H+L) Highly Cross-Adsorbed

Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor™ Plus 647 (Catalog # A32728) or Goat anti-Rabbit IgG (H+L) Highly Cross-Adsorbed Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor™ 647 (Catalog # A21245) (1:500 dilution, 90 minutes incubation at 4°C, from ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). Analysis was performed using FACS Canto II (BD Biosciences, NJ, USA) and FlowJo version 10 software (FlowJo LLC, Ashland, Orlando, USA). Mean fluorescence was obtained from at least 50000 gated events per sample. For each sample, at least 3 independent replicates were performed. For the immunocytochemistry protocol, cells were allowed to grow in glass coverslips and, afterwards, were washed and fixed in 4% PFA (v/v) (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) in 1x PBS. Then, cells were incubated with NH₄Cl 50mM (v/v) in 1x PBS to limit cell autofluorescence and with 0,2% TritonX-100 (v/v) (Sigma, St. Louis, MO, USA) in 1x PBS to destabilize the cell membrane. Cells were incubated with the same primary antibodies used in flow cytometry: mouse anti alpha Catenin Monoclonal Antibody alpha-CAT-7A4 (1:200 dilution) or rabbit anti Catenin alpha-1 Monoclonal Antibody (J.783.6) (1:50 dilution) (overnight incubation at 4°C). The same secondary antibodies from flow cytometry were also used: Goat anti-Mouse or Goat anti-Rabbit IgG (H+L) Highly Cross-Adsorbed Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor™ Plus 647 (1:500 dilution, 2h incubation at room temperature). At last, cells were incubated in 1µg/mL DAPI (CAS Number 28718-90-3, 1µg/m, Sigma-Aldrich, Poole, UK) in 1x PBS and mounted in Vectashield anti-fade mounting media (Vector Laboratories, Burlingame, CA, USA). Cell fluorescence was analysed using ZEISS Axiovert 200M Inverted fluorescence microscope (Zeiss, Gottingen, Germany) and AxioVision software (Rockville, MD, USA). For each sample, at least 2 independent replicates were performed.

4. NMD blockade assay

To understand if NMD was a mechanism for *CTNNA1* Ex11Del, cycloheximide NMD blockade was performed. Briefly, MKN74 wild-type and *CTNNA1* Ex11Del cells were plated in 6-well plates for approximately 72 hours. When ~80% confluency was obtained, cells were incubated with 2mL of medium containing cycloheximide at 0.1mg/mL concentration. Medium containing sterile water was used as a vehicle control. Cells were incubated in either cycloheximide or sterile water for 6 hours and, afterwards, total RNA was isolated using the mirVana™ miRNA Isolation Kit (# AM1561; Invitrogen™, Carlsbad, CA, USA), cDNA was synthesized using SuperScript® II reverse transcriptase from ThermoFisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA), and RT-qPCR was performed as described above. For each cell line, cells incubated in medium with sterile water were used as control. At least 3 independent replicates were performed.

Development of a humanized Drosophila melanogaster model to study CTNNA1 variants' functional impact:

1. Experiment layout

To obtain “humanized” *Drosophila* lines, Gal4/UAS system was used. This allowed to modulate α-Catenin expression in *Drosophila* target organs (eyes) and is based on two main components: 1) Gal4, which is a yeast transcriptional activator whose expression is modulated by tissue-specific

promoters, allowing tissue-specific altered α -Catenin expression; and 2) upstream activating sequences (UAS) targeting α -Catenin and in which expression is dependent of Gal4 due to its Gal4-binding sites. These are combined in the flies' offspring, upon which become activated specifically in the cell type where Gal4 expression is driven.

To this study, Optix-Gal4 driver was used, which targets the undifferentiated eye progenitor cells from the eye-antenna imaginal disk from *Drosophila*. To deplete the *Drosophila* version of α -Catenin, the α -Cat RNAi (Bloomington *Drosophila* Stock Center: 33430; TRiP: HMS00317, Harvard Medical School) was used. UAS LacZ was used as an experiment control. All UAS human CTNNA1 lines used are listed in Supplemental Table 7.

2. Site directed mutagenesis

The *CTNNA1* variants to be used in the *Drosophila* model were obtained through site directed mutagenesis, as previously described (Fisher and Pei 1997). Briefly, 15ng of pDONR221 vector with the *CTNNA1* cDNA gene inserted (#HsCD00043267, from DNASU plasmid repository, Tempe, AZ, USA) was mixed with 2.5 units of Pfu DNA polymerase, 10mM dNTP and 0.5 μ M forward and reverse primers (Alfagene, Carcavelos, Portugal) specifically designed to contain the desired mutation. The mix was then incubated in a thermocycler with the following program: one round at 95°C for 45 seconds; 18 cycles at 95°C for 45 seconds, sample specific annealing temperature for 45 seconds and 72°C for 10 minutes (2 minutes per 1Kb); and one final extension at 72°C for 10 minutes. After, PCR product is mixed with 10 units of DpnI restriction enzyme. This is a Dam Methylation-Sensitive restriction enzyme that will cut any methylated DNA, which is the case of the parental non-mutated *CTNNA1* cDNA pDONR221 vector. Later, 2 μ L of PCR product were mixed with 50 μ L of DH5 α bacteria, followed by heat shock (42°C for 45 seconds). Bacteria are then plated in LB agar plates with kanamycin resistance and allowed to grow overnight. Five isolated colonies were harvested, cultured in LB broth with kanamycin resistance and DNA prepped for screening by Sanger sequencing for the mutated region. For that, 100 ng of plasmid DNA were mixed with 0.8 μ L of BigDye™ Terminator v3.1 Cycle Sequencing Kit from Applied Biosystems (Foster City, CA, USA), 1 μ L of BigDye buffer, 0.4 μ L of each sample specific primer at 10 μ M and 5.8 μ L of sterile water. Samples were incubated in a thermocycler and PCR products were subsequently purified using Sephadex® G-50 (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany), mixed with 12 μ L of formamide (Applied Biosystems, Waltham, MA, USA) and analysed with the Applied Biosystems 3130xl Genetic Analyzer (Applied Biosystems, Waltham, MA, USA). One colony containing each desired *CTNNA1* variant proceeded to be cloned into a destination vector using Gateway® technology (ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA).

3. Gateway® cloning

Gateway® technology (ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) was used to clone the *CTNNA1* cDNA sequence into the pPW-attB destination vector (DNASU Plasmid Repository). This vector contains 14 upstream activation sequences, followed by a P-element that will allow the integration of *CTNNA1* cDNA (either wild-type or mutated versions) in the fly genome by

directed transposition. It also contains the *White* reporter gene, which is used to select flies containing the sequence of interest. To perform Gateway®, 150ng of the entry vector were mixed with 150ng of the destination vector and LR Clonase II restriction enzyme (ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). This allowed the insert of *CTNNA1* cDNA sequence into the pPW-attB vector by swapping the sequences within the attL and the attR sites, which are the *CTNNA1* cDNA sequence and a toxic *ccdB* gene sequence, respectively. After transformation as described above with an ampicillin resistance, DH5 α colonies containing the pPW-attB-*CTNNA1* cDNA (wild-type or mutated versions) were obtained. This DNA is subsequently amplified, maxi-prepped (Plasmid Maxi kit from Qiagen, Venlo, Netherlands) and Sanger sequenced to confirm presence of the desired mutation.

Subsequently, human constructs were inserted into the VK33 docking sites using ϕ C31-mediated transgenesis in *Drosophila* embryos (Bischof et al. 2007) at the Zurich ORFeome Project (Zurich, Switzerland).

4. Survival assay

Fly crosses were performed at 25°C, under standard conditions. Supplementary Table 7 contains all the fly stocks used to conduct the experiments. In the lethality assays, vials were analysed every 1-3 days for live adult flies according to genotype. All adult flies were counted and emerging from pupae to adult fly was represented as the relative survival, after normalization to a viability control. Each cross was performed at least 3 times.

5. Protein expression analysis

To analyse α -catenin protein absence/presence in the specific tissue driving adult organ formation, late third instar larvae were used. Herein, only larvae containing the specific human transgene for each cross were selected. For that, only larvae not comprising the TM6B balancer chromosome phenotype were used in the immunohistochemistry protocol. Briefly, eye-antennal or wing imaginal discs were dissected in cold 1x PBS and further fixed in 3.7% PFA (v/v) (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) in 1x PBS for 25 minutes at room temperature. Afterwards, disks were washed in 0.1% Triton® X-100 (v/v) (Sigma, St. Louis, MO, USA) in 1x PBS and the following primary antibodies were used: rat anti- *Drosophila* alpha-catenin (1:100 dilution, 2 hours and 30 minutes incubation at room temperature, AB_532377 from Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, DSHB, Iowa City, IA, USA); mouse anti alpha Catenin Monoclonal Antibody alpha-CAT-7A4 (1:200 dilution, 2 hours and 30 minutes incubation at room temperature, #13-9700 from ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). Appropriate Alexa Fluor conjugated secondary antibodies to be used in these experiments were purchased from Molecular Probes: Alexa Fluor® 488 anti-mouse (1:1000, 1 hour and 30 minutes incubation at room temperature); Alexa Fluor® 568 anti-rat (1:1000, 1 hour and 30 minutes incubation at room temperature). Vectashield mounting media with DAPI (Vector Laboratories, Burlingame, CA, USA) was used to mount the imaginal discs. Fluorescence was measured using the Leica SP5II confocal microscope and analysed using Leica Application Suite X (Leica, Wetzlar, Germany).

Statistical analysis:

Continuous variables (age-of-onset, YY) are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD), categorical variables (phenotypes, XX) are presented as counts (%) and were respectively compared using t-test or Mann–Whitney test and χ^2 or Fischer exact's tests, when adequate. Phenotypes without an associated age-of-onset were excluded from statistical analyses. Multiple comparisons of age of disease onset in carrier probands and their relatives and different types of variants, were done using a Kruskal-Wallis test with Bonferroni correction. Logistic regression, adjusted for age, sex, and self-reported ethnicity, was used to compare GC and LBC frequencies among *CTNNA1* and *CDH1* carriers in Cohort-IV. Pearson correlation was used to identify independent phenotypes for variants with distinct predicted impact in the protein (truncating vs. non-truncating). Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Statistical analyses, estimation of performance parameters, and graphical content were carried out using IBM SPSS Statistics v29 and RStudio v. 4.3.2 with ggstatsplot v. 0.12.2, ggplot2 v.3.5.1³⁰, and logistf v.1.26.0 packages. To evaluate the likelihood of each set of criteria producing false positive and false negative results, we calculated the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value, with corresponding 95% CIs, using R (version 4.1.3) with the library epiR (version 2.0.50) (Stevenson & Sergeant 2025), whereas the Youden index (J) used to estimate the criteria's discriminating power, and the corresponding 95% CIs, were computed with the library ThresholdROC (Perez-Jaume et al. 2017). The term 'Classic' criteria represents a combination of the 2020 HDGC clinical criteria (Blair et al. 2020) plus the 2023 Lobular breast cancer expanded criteria proposed by Garcia-Pelaez et al.; the 'Classic + *CTNNA1* expanded' criteria combines the previous set of criteria with two extra criteria designed specifically in this study for *CTNNA1* genetic testing; 'Porto' criteria summarizes the 'Classic + *CTNNA1* expanded' criteria from 14 to five criteria topics; 'Yale' criteria represents the HDGC+HBOC clinical criteria proposed by Lerner and colleagues (Lerner et al. 2025, Hodan et al. 2024). To compare performance in terms of true positive or true negative detection for different abovementioned sets of clinical criteria, equivalence tests and corresponding 95% CIs were computed in R by directly implementing formulae. The equivalence limit (δ) was set to 0.12 (Walker & Nowacki 2011). Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$ for all statistical tests.

Statistical analysis related with the development of *CTNNA1 in vitro* and *in vivo* functional models was performed using GraphPad Prism version 8.0.2 for Windows (GraphPad Software, Boston, Massachusetts USA, www.graphpad.com). Statistically significant results were established by two-tailed paired t-test (* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$; **** $p < 0.0001$).

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